

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES

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**Disability Benefit Package for Children
with Developmental Disabilities (CDDs) in the Philippines:
A Policy Analysis**

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8 February 2023

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**DISABILITY BENEFIT PACKAGE FOR CHILDREN
WITH DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILITIES (CDDs) IN THE PHILIPPINES:
A POLICY ANALYSIS**

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled: “**DISABILITY BENEFIT PACKAGE FOR CHILDREN WITH DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILITIES (CDDs) IN THE PHILIPPINES: A POLICY ANALYSIS**,” is hereby accepted Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

I am Pauline Gail V. Martinez, DipIH, OTRP. I finished my undergraduate degree, BS Occupational Therapy (OT), in 2016 at the University of the Philippines – Manila. Last 2021, I graduated from my Diploma in International Health post-graduate degree at UP Open University.

I am an occupational therapist who have served children with developmental disabilities (CDDs) in my hometown, Pampanga, for the past six years. I have also served as the program chair and a faculty member of an undergraduate OT program in a private university in the same province. Over the years, I have been involved with research projects and pursued my interests in OT education, occupational science, interprofessional education and collaborative practice, and disability studies. With these roles and experiences, I decided to pursue the International Health graduate program in order to have a wider perspective of the health system in the local and global setting. I believed that with learning about the best practices in the world, I can be more equipped in helping make rehabilitation services more accessible especially for the CDDs and their families.

After earning my post-graduate diploma degree, I applied for the Master of International Health program in order to advance my research and advocacy. I hope that through a study that investigates the current policy implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs through our national health insurance, key stakeholders will be more informed and equipped in lobbying for the necessary policy reforms. Thus, more CDDs can benefit from the disability benefit packages, achieve better health outcomes, and improve quality of life.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincerest gratitude to the several people who supported me in finishing this endeavor. First and foremost, my thesis adviser, Dr. Michael P. Sy, for being a source of motivation, inspiration, and guidance in this academic requirement. Second, I am extending my gratitude to the faculty of management and development studies led by Dr. Myra D. Oruga for molding us to have an international health perspective to help improve the current status of the health system and help achieve better health outcomes in the country. Third, I would like to thank my family, especially my parents, for instilling in me the value of education and for the unconditional love and support given. Fourth, I appreciate the support of my friends for sharing their enthusiasm and monitoring my progress over the past year. Fifth, thank you to the invited validators and participants who generously shared their time and insights in the hopes of contributing to improving access to therapy services for children with developmental disabilities. Lastly, I thank God for the strength, wisdom, and grace I received.

Dedication

To the Filipino children with developmental disabilities and their families

Abstract

Background: Sustainable development goal declarations influenced various countries across the globe to create and reform laws and policies to achieve universal health care (UHC). To improve access to the health of children with developmental disabilities (CDDs), PhilHealth launched the Z benefit package for CDDs, which offers subsidized rehabilitation assessments and interventions from contracted healthcare institutions. However, this policy remains underutilized.

Research Objectives: This study aimed to analyze the factors that influence the implementation of the disability benefits package for CDDs in the Philippines. Specifically, to 1) describe the current context, policy actors, content, and process of the disability benefits package for CDDs; 2) explore perspectives of policy actors towards implementation of the disability benefits package and their critiques on the context, content, and process of the policy; and 3) identify the facilitators and barriers that influence the implementation of the disability benefits package for CDDs.

Methodology: The study used a case study design which entailed the collection of data through document review of policy documents and focused group discussions (FGDs) among selected policy actors (i.e., rehabilitation professionals, representatives from professional organizations, administrative heads of institutions, parents of CDDs). Guided by Walt and Gilson's policy triangle framework (Walt and Gilson, 1994), data were analyzed through content analysis via a deductive approach.

Results: Twenty-two (22) policy documents were retrieved in the document review and a total of 16 participants joined the FGDs. Facilitators and barriers were identified and categorized through the policy elements: 1) context is anchored

through the presence of laws and policies supporting the advocacy of early intervention and access to therapy services of CDDs but is hindered by issues on politics, governance and labor force; 2) policy actors (service providers and beneficiaries) are hopeful in the continuous implementation of the Z benefit package nationwide and share the advocacy for CDDs but is hindered by the limited participation of all potential policy actors and limitations with human resources; 3) content is sound and comprehensive but concerns on costing and complying with required resources hinder translation to implementation and lack of certain protocols posit threat on adaptability and sustainability; and 4) processes involved in implementation emphasize quality assurance and initial dissemination efforts were effective during launch but the lack of activities to continuously engage potential service providers and the tediousness of overall process limits participation of service providers both from the public and private sectors.

Conclusion: While the launch of the disability benefits package for CDDs in the Philippines seemed promising, the policy remains underutilized as the identified barriers outweigh the facilitators of each policy element. Thus, recommendations for policy reform, education, and research were derived to improve future policy implementation.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vi
Table of Contents	ix
List of Tables	xi
List of Figures	xii
ABSTRACT	vii
CHAPTER I: THE RESEARCH PROBLEM	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	3
Objectives of the Study	4
Significance of the Study	4
Scope and Limitation of the Study	5
CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	7
Review of Literature	7
PhilHealth's Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities	8
Theoretical Framework	11
Health Policy and Processes	11
Health Policy Analysis	12
Conceptual Framework	13
Operational Definition	15
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	17
Research Design	17
Data Collection	18
Data Analysis	25
Rigor and Trustworthiness	27
Ethical Considerations	29

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	30	
Results	30	
Factors influencing the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs	38	
Discussion	57	
CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	64	
REFERENCES	00	
APPENDICES		
Appendix A	Recommended questions for document review adopted from Dalglish et al. (2020) and Cheung et al. (2010)	84
Appendix B	Sample email invitation to participants	85
Appendix C	Poster for parents of CDDs	86
Appendix D	Google Form for parents of CDDs	87
Appendix E	Filipino translation of focus group discussion questions	92
Appendix F	Summary of codes from the FGD	96
Appendix G	Informed Consent Forms	100
Appendix H	Certificate of exemption from UP Manila Research Ethics Board	109
Appendix I	Curriculum Vitae	111

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1	Summary of codes from document review.....	20
Table 3.2	General questions used in the FGD.....	22
Table 3.3	Specific questions for each FGD cohort.....	23
Table 3.4	Categorization matrix (Sample from the FGD with Parents of CDD).....	26
Table 4.1	List of documents reviewed for policy analysis.....	30
Table 4.2	Demographic profile of participants.....	36
Table 5	Specific recommendations for the disability benefit package for CDDs.....	67

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1	Conceptual framework.....	16
Figure 3	Audit of data collection and data analysis.....	28
Figure 4	Summary of facilitators and barriers in the Z benefit package for CDDs	56

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

One of the ways to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3, which aims to “ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages” (United Nations, 2015), is through universal health coverage (UHC). The UHC facilitates financial risk security giving people access to quality, essential, and affordable healthcare services, thus achieving health equity (Tangcharoensathien et al., 2015). Through the SDG declarations, shaping international health policies were through the following initiatives: 1) putting and sustaining health financing reforms for UHC on the national agenda and 2) providing enabling context for debating and passing health laws and reviewing national health policies to strengthen health financing systems for UHC (Odoch et al., 2021).

Since the developing countries began accepting UHC, they started facilitating policy processes, such as agenda setting, formulation, implementation, evaluation, and monitoring. In 2018, the World Health Organization (WHO) defined policy as “health goals at the international, national, or local level and specifies the decisions, plans, and actions to be undertaken to achieve these goals.” The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention ([CDC], 2019) further classifies policy as “a law, regulation, procedure, administrative action, incentive or voluntary practice of governments and other institutions.”

For a developing country like the Philippines, passing the Universal Healthcare Act or Republic Act (RA) 11223 as a legislative policy in 2019 was crucial

and marked the beginning of the country's commitment to attaining SDG 3. Since this is a milestone for the Philippine healthcare system, it became a big challenge for the country fully implement the law. Within the Philippine healthcare system, 60% and 54% of hospitals are privatized and categorized as out-of-the-pocket expenses of the overall health expenditure, respectively (Capuno et al., 2021). One essential method to facilitate the expansion of coverage is through the national health insurance, Philippine Health Insurance (PhilHealth), which serves as a regulatory policy that implements the mandatory contribution scheme that pools money from the citizens at a national level and purchases a package of health services for all insured members (Kutzin, 2012).

All Filipino citizens can benefit from PhilHealth, especially the poor and the marginalized. One of the groups experiencing poverty is children with disabilities (CWDs). In a 2018 report by UNICEF, there are more than 5 million Filipino CWDs. Findings showed that poverty rates were 50% higher in families with CWDs compared to families with typically-developing children and that only one of five (20%) of these families with CWDs availed of a disability identification card to be used to benefit from the 20% discount on daily expenses (Carraro et al., 2022). Furthermore, the study also emphasized the need to increase awareness of disability registration, improve referral systems, and intensify advocacy and information on educational and rehabilitation interventions (Carraro et al., 2022).

To increase access to rehabilitation needs, PhilHealth launched a policy in 2018 called the Z Benefit Package for children with developmental disabilities (CDDs). The Z Benefit Package is a promising scheme that ensures financial risk protection and prevents catastrophic pocket expenditure in order to access quality

healthcare services (PhilHealth, 2018). Specifically, the package includes assessment, planning, rehabilitation therapy sessions, and discharge plans by a medical specialist and rehabilitation professionals (i.e., occupational therapist, physical therapist, speech or language pathologist).

To receive the Z Benefit Package, CDDs shall enlist and avail of the needed healthcare services from a contracted healthcare institution (HCI). Based on the PhilHealth Circular 2017-0029, PhilHealth (2017) had engaged with identified tertiary government hospitals for the specialized provision services under the Z benefit package. After the pilot test with public hospitals, there should be subsequent contracting by encouraging both public and private HCI to be contracted service providers to expand utilization and implementation efficiency. Contracted HCIs are privileged to provide care to PhilHealth members and can exercise the right to reimburse payment for rehabilitation services. Four years after its launch, as of June 2022, there are only four HCI accredited for the Z benefit package for CDDs: two (2) in National Capital Region, one (1) in Leyte (Region 8), and one (1) Davao (Region 11) (PhilHealth, 2022a).

Statement of the Problem

Even without available statistical data on service utilization in the Philippines, four HCIs are insufficient to cater to the estimated 5 million CWDs across 81 provinces. Thus, the Z benefit package for CDDs remains underutilized. Identifying and understanding the factors behind its underutilization warrants an examination of overall components, including the actors in this policy, relevant influencing context,

content explaining the policy design, and processes contingent on the implementation.

Objectives of the Study

Thus, this study sought to analyze the factors that influence the implementation of the disability benefits package for CDDs in the Philippines. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Describe the current context, policy actors, content, and process of the disability benefits package for CDDs;
2. Explore perspectives of policy actors towards implementation of the disability benefits package and their critiques on the context, content, and process of the policy;
3. Identify the facilitators and barriers that influence the implementation of the disability benefits package for CDDs.

Significance of the Study

Four years after launching the policy, there is underwhelming progress in the number of accredited HCI in this particular disability benefits package for CDDs in the Philippines (PhilHealth, 2022a). Engaging in this systematic investigation to raise awareness of the promising policy scheme and emphasizing the significance of maximizing health policies, especially for citizens from marginalized groups in low to middle-income countries, is relevant.

Additional to the current literature on international health, this study intends to encourage other countries that have yet to develop policies on disability benefit packages for CWDs to learn from the evaluation of factors to effectively formulate, evaluate and reform policies. Several authors (Walt et al., 2008; Makan et al., 2015; Shaikh, 2018) emphasized the importance of health policy analyses to provide evidence-informed feedback to policymakers and catalyze change through holistic document review and stakeholder engagement.

The engagement of stakeholders taps on intersectoral collaboration and action, acknowledging the variety of actors (i.e., public and private sectors, non-governmental organizations (NGO), parents of CDDs, CDDs) who have critical roles in the ongoing evaluation of policies and active participation on reforms to improve implementation. Public and private healthcare institution administrators and the rehabilitation professionals (i.e., developmental pediatricians, occupational therapists, physical therapists, and speech therapists) will be able to practice shared duty and accountability in facilitating the extension of access to financially-challenged parents and CDDs.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focused on the specific policy by PhilHealth entitled the Z benefit package for CDDs and its current status of implementation from 2018 up to August 2022. Since this study is one of the few existing studies to systematically look at the factors influencing this specific policy, presenting an overview of components categorized through the policy triangle framework is relevant. Hence, the factors'

breadth, instead of depth, was targeted. Specific mechanisms, such as health financing, including financial indexes, are not part of the study.

Guided by the policy triangle framework by Walt and Gilson (2004), actors play a central role in policy, shaping study results by their inputs and were cross-referenced by policy documents. In the study, the chosen actors composed of external stakeholders such as HCI administrators, rehabilitation professionals, professional organizations, and parents of CDDs, which were usually known to have limited involvement in decision-making during policy formulation and implementation (Maurer et al., 2022; Patil et al., 2021; Boax et al., 2018). The internal stakeholders, such as the PhilHealth and the Department of Health (DOH) staff, were not involved, limiting the possible views and interpretations of the study.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Related Literature

International Health Perspectives on Disability Benefit Packages for Children

A disability benefits package is one of the social insurance schemes where all insured members are entitled to specific health benefits. The benefits package typically includes a list of comprehensive requirements for member registration, service provision, funding, and contracting of healthcare providers (Normand et al., 2009). This kind of social protection is a lifeline for families raising children with disabilities suffering from poverty due to disability-associated costs and lost earning opportunities for parents to look after their children (UNICEF, 2019). In 2011, the WHO estimated that around 200 million children in the world and young people have impairments causing disability, and about 80% of CWDs live in developing countries.

Aside from SDG 3, which aimed for health equity for all through the UHC, there were also other SDGs interconnected with CWDs, such as the SDGs 4, 11, and 17, which target access to quality education for all, sustainable and inclusive communities, and strengthening partnerships and collaborations, respectively (United Nations, 2015). Additionally, several international standards and mechanisms highlight the commitment to protect the rights of CWDs and improve their access to services. For instance, Article 23 of the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child instigated the obligation of State parties and ensured children with disabilities enjoy a full and decent life (United Nations, 1989). Additionally, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities initiated a paradigm shift from

a medical model to a social model of disability, which emphasizes the eradication of attitudinal and environmental barriers that can hinder persons with disabilities from achieving their full capacity (United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2006). Regionally, these provisions through the ASEAN Enabling Masterplan 2025 are being employed, which sets the priority on CWDs, such that disability and age-appropriate programs and services are provided to them (ASEAN, 2018).

International health helps one learn perspectives beyond the borders of one's country, such as viewing challenges and the solutions that affect low and middle-income countries in their journey to promote health through an international health lens (Chen et al., 2020; Merson et al., 2006). Some countries, such as Argentina, Finland, Japan, and South Africa, have international health experiences collated in report by the Faculty of Social Administration of Thammasat University and UNICEF in 2019. Argentina introduced a universal child allowance program wherein they give four times the standard rate of receiving between 110 USD to 493 USD to indigent families with CWD. However, there was a lack of data on the access of families of CWD to needed healthcare services. In Finland and Japan, linking cash to health services was emphasized and classified as a best practice, as CWDs are able to receive in-kind services that help children cope with daily tasks. The services provided in Finland and Japan are classified depending on the age and severity of the disability, respectively. In South Africa, the processing of disability benefits was a big obstacle due to the lengthy and complex process involving several visits to institutions and long waiting times. This problem magnifies the gaps between the existence of the disability benefits package and its utilization.

PhilHealth's Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities

The Z benefit package is offered to PhilHealth members to accommodate their needs that necessitate prolonged hospitalization and expensive treatments. Letter Z, as the last letter in the alphabet, reflects the farthest end of the spectrum of diseases in terms of being perceived as catastrophic and concerning financial and physiological burdens (PhilHealth, 2012). Examples of illnesses covered are cancer, heart conditions, chronic kidney disease, orthopedic conditions, and premature and newborn concerns. Z benefit package also includes four different packages specific for children with disabilities:

1. hearing impairment
2. visual impairment
3. mobility impairment
4. developmental disability

For this study, the focus is on the Z benefit package for CDDs, which among the four benefit packages, covers the highest number of possible recipients because of the range of conditions classified as developmental disabilities. This type of disability refers to either activity limitation or participation restriction secondary to a delay, regression, or loss in the developmental milestone of a child, which can be neurological or non-neurological in origin (PhilHealth, 2018b). Children living with this condition are needed to be diagnosed by a developmental pediatrician and may need to receive individualized therapy sessions from occupational therapists, physical therapists, and speech therapists. These specialized services are often inaccessible to poor communities.

The Z benefit package for CDDs was launched in 2017, namely the PhilHealth Z benefit package for CDDs. The timely passing of RA 11223, also known as the

Universal Health Care Act, in 2018 strengthened the commitment of the government to improve access to healthcare services by decreasing the financial burden in coordination with PhilHealth. In the same year, RA 11228 (2018), the amendment of the Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities, mandated the automatic enrolment of PWDs to the national insurance system and ordered the government to shoulder the required premium contributions for PWDs. Laws and policies supporting the disability benefits package are promising strategies to ensure the social protection of CWDs. However, the implementation of these laws and policies is another subject matter.

The PhilHealth Z benefit package for CDDs is underutilized and generally remains inaccessible because there are only four contracted HCIs in the Philippines. The implementation of this policy heavily depends on the availability of services which relies on the number of contracted HCIs by the national social health insurance. Picazo and colleagues (2015) criticized PhilHealth benefit packages for assistive devices needed by PWDs and stated that low utilization is because there is a limited number of providers and patient information and stringent eligibility criteria. They also explained how PhilHealth as a purchaser of health services to providers, is far from achieving the ideal functions of the purchaser in the purchaser-provider relationship. These functions include taking dynamic decisions from providers, enforcing contractual agreements with qualified public and private providers, adjusting payment methods, and ensuring mutual accountability through timely payment, among others (Picazo et al., 2015). Thus, considering more facilitative arrangements with providers must be recommended.

PhilHealth's Z benefit package is open for public and private sector providers (PhilHealth, 2018). The public sector refers to government-run institutions and those

publicly funded agencies. On the other hand, the private sector is individuals and organizations not controlled by the government. These providers are considered policy actors who hold administrative positions in various HCI (i.e., hospitals, therapy clinic managers, and representatives from professional associations and non-governmental organizations) that deliver specialized services (i.e., rehabilitation medicine, developmental pediatrics, occupational therapy (OT), physical therapy (PT) and speech therapy (ST)). Capeding and colleagues (2020) emphasized that effective contracting of public and private sectors could improve equity and utilization, but there is a dearth of literature discussing how issues and barriers to contracting need addressing. There is a need for discussions among policy actors to establish a consensus on performance indicators and to identify strategies and mechanisms (Capeding et al., 2020; Lemke and Harris-Wai, 2015; Masefield et al., 2021) that bridge the gap in the implementation of policies related to the national social insurance.

Theoretical Framework

Health Policy and Processes

According to WHO (2021), health policy “defines health goals at the international, national, or local level and specifies the decisions, plans, and actions to be undertaken to achieve these goals.” Health policy is a principal component of the Ottawa Charter for Health Promotion (WHO, 1986) which emphasizes “coordinated action that leads to health, income, and social policies that foster greater equity.”

Based on the Howlett and Ramesh’s model, policy development includes five stages (Howlett et al., 2020; Benoit, 2013):

- 1) agenda setting – identification of the problem to be addressed by the policy;
- 2) formulation – consideration of possible solutions through discussion of involved actors and determination of the direction of the policy;
- 3) adoption – decision-making at the governmental level in choosing the approaches to be utilized in addressing the problem;
- 4) implementation – application of policy intentions and resources into actions to achieve the policy outcomes;
- 5) evaluation – assessment of employed interventions and outcomes for future reform.

Health Policy Analysis

Undertaking policy analysis is usually in the process of policy formulation or evaluation. Health policy analysis is defined as *“the role of policy actors in policy change, how they influence and are themselves influenced by contextual factors, why and how they react to policy design details, the processes contingent on developing and implementing policy and how power plays out in these processes”* (Gilson et al., 2018, p.11). In this definition, Walt and Gilson (1994) argued that policy actors have a central role in impacting policy changes when the relationship between context, process, and content of policy is clarified. It is crucial to recognize the views of policy actors to reconcile policy goals and agree on the revision of specific mechanisms.

The gathering of evidence from health policy analyses informs policymakers which could increase the chances of successful implementation (Collins, 2005;

Cheung et al., 2010; Gilson and Raphaely, 2008). However, there is a dearth of literature on health policy analysis in low-and middle-income countries (LMIC). In a literature review of published health policy analyses from 1994 to 2007 by Gilson and Raphaely (2008), the authors stated that this area of research remains in its infancy in LMIC. Of the 391 articles reviewed, 11 (2.81%) were about insurance relating to universal health coverage, but 0% published articles that focused on disability benefits. Furthermore, the authors argued that politics, process, and power concepts should be considered achieved through “deliberative engagement with policymakers, advocacy groups, and or civil society organizations” (Gilson and Raphaely, 2008, p. 304).

Conceptual Framework

Guided by Walt and Gilson's (1994) health policy framework (See Figure 1), performing policy analysis is essential to study the factors that affect the implementation of this disability benefits package. The policy analysis (Walt and Gilson, 1994, Gilson et al., 2001) includes these four elements:

- 1) Context: refers to the macro-contextual factors that influence the Z benefit package for CDD involving the socio-economic context of implementation, financing patterns of the health system, cultural practices, and other governing mechanisms;
- 2) Content: refers to the design of the Z benefit package for CDD, including the fees, retention and revenue practices, exemption scheme, and community involvement in decision-making;

- 3) **Process:** refers to the specific mechanisms and manner of implementation and the means of involving stakeholders in designing and implementing the Z benefit package for CDD;
- 4) **Policy Actors:** refers to the people and groups involved in decision-making and implementation, which also encompasses their interests, concerns, and roles in the execution of the Z benefit package for CDD.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

The triangulation reflects the interrelatedness of the policy actors, context, content, and process affecting policy implementation. The actors at the center of the triangle exemplify their vital roles in achieving the set outcomes of the policy. Walt and Gilson (1994) argued that most analyses focus on context or process alone. With the addition of context and the emphasis that policy actors do not only involve the public sector alone, this adapted framework also aims to be holistic.

Through a health policy analysis, facilitators and barriers on the policy elements, i.e., context, content, process, and actors, shall be determined. Facilitators are the supporting factors, while barriers are the hindering factors of policy implementation.

Findings can potentially contribute to the baseline knowledge of the national social insurance policy regarding the Z benefit package for CDDs. This policy analysis may help draw evidence-informed recommendations for reforms of the target policy in the Philippines and other countries with similar contexts.

Operational Definition

Policy. This refers to defined health goals at international, national, and local levels that stipulate decisions and actions to be undertaken to achieve aims. In this study, the policy in focus is PhilHealth's Z benefit package for CDDs.

Policy Actors. This pertains to people or stakeholders involved in the decision-making and implementation of a specific policy. For this study, the actors are mainly the HCI administrative heads, rehabilitation professionals, representatives from professional organizations, and parents of CDDs.

Administrative heads. These are people who serve as the chief, department head, and manager of a hospital or therapy center.

Rehabilitation professionals. These are licensed and certified developmental pediatricians, occupational therapists, physical therapists, and speech-language pathologists employed in a hospital or therapy center.

Representatives from professional organizations. These are active board members of respective professional organizations from developmental pediatrics, OT, PT, and SLP who were sent to serve as a resource person for the study.

Parents of CDDs. These refer to biological parents of CDDs who also serve as primary caregivers of their children as they undergo rehabilitation services prescribed. They can also be parents who are members or leaders of PWD organizations for CDDs.

Context. This pertains to the status of the healthcare systems and other socio-economic factors that affect policy implementation.

Content. This refers to the design of the policy in terms of inclusions, benefits, and requirements among others.

Process. This refers to the mechanisms involved in policy implementation and the manner of involvement of stakeholders in the design and formulation of policy.

Facilitator. This refers to a supporting element or identified strength in policy implementation.

Barrier. This refers to hindrances or identified weaknesses in policy implementation.

Private sector. This pertains to institutions independent from the government and owned by private individuals or groups of people.

Public Sector. This pertains to institutions owned and run by the government.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative study used a case study design (Yin, 2018), which focused on the Z benefit package for CDDs as a policy and investigated each element of the policy triangle by Walt and Gilson (1994). This study design enabled the researcher to explore the case by employing a variety of data sources in the premise of a constructivist approach. Walt and colleagues (2008) also reported the applicability of case studies in health policy analysis because of their ability to understand the gap in policy implementation and produce sound recommendations beyond the case itself.

The study employed a combination of data collection methods: 1) document review and 2) focus group discussion (FGD) of the identified policy actors. The first method supplied the available information on published documents concerning mainly the policy's context, content, and process and less on policy actors except for their specified roles and responsibilities stipulated in the documents. The document review emphasizes the value of objectivity, in which the collected information can be triangulated with the collected subjective information from the policy actors themselves (Dalglish et al., 2020). The second method involved the policy actors as they shared their perspectives on their roles as policy actors and their views on the context, content, and process. Kahan (2001) argues that FGD, along with one-one interviews with key informants, is part of the standard toolkit in policy analysis. The diversity of policy actors and their differing perspectives on the policy enables a researcher to investigate how these differences affect policy implementation. The

combination of these data collection methods (i.e., document review and FGD/interviews) has been used in numerous studies for health policy analyses in developing countries like Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Zambia, Nigeria, and Pakistan (El-Jardali et al., 2014; Pearson et al., 2010; Mukanu et al., 2017; Mbachu et al., 2016; Ahmed et al., 2021). While none of these policy analyses were about disability, these policy analysis studies focused on nursing practice, suicide, non-communicable diseases, and maternal and child health.

Data Collection

Document Review

The document review adopted the READ approach by Dalglish et al. (2020), which offers a systematic step-by-step process of collecting documents and gathering information for health policy studies. The steps consisted of 1) Ready your materials, 2) Extract data, 3) Analyze data, and 4) Distill your findings. These four steps led to accumulating relevant policy documents and reviewing them to get a holistic picture of the policy.

Step 1: Ready your materials

The study conducted research through the national health insurance website (www.philhealth.gov.ph), news, and government websites via Google and social media (Facebook and Twitter). The “Z benefit package AND children AND developmental disabilities” search combination was used. The type of documents to be reviewed included a mix of formal documents (i.e., official policies, laws, strategies, gray literature, reports, evaluation, and publication material) and informal documents (i.e., memoranda, PowerPoint presentations) (Dalglish et al., 2020).

Included were the documents that satisfy the following inclusion criteria: 1) address the policy in focus -Z benefit package for CDDs, and 2) relate to the policy elements of the Z benefit package for CDDs. Documents were classified into Yes, Maybe, and No. The initial search was in the first week of August 2022. A total of 285 documents were included for title screening, composed of 83 hits on the PhilHealth website, the first 100 hits on Google, and the first 100 hits on Facebook, and screened all two (hits) on Twitter. After the title screening, 66 documents, wherein 32 Yes and 34 Maybe, were retrieved for full-text screening. Common reasons for exclusions were: 1) the document is unrelated, and 2) the document is about Z benefits but not for CDDs. The articles classified as “Maybe” included short titles containing acronyms and numerals in their titles, which necessitated a full-text review. Twenty-three documents, after the full-text screening, were included. The document is either unrelated, maybe related, such as financial reports, but is out of the scope of the study, or included forms already in the annexes of appended policy documents.

Step 2: Extract data

Some information from the included documents, e.i., document title, author, year published, URL, and purpose, was extracted in an Excel sheet.

Step 3: Analyze data

After extracting the data, recommended questions for policy analysis from Dalglish and colleagues (2020) were also utilized as a guide (See Appendix A: Recommended questions for document review). The researcher added columns to

the Excel Sheet to categorize key elements noted in the documents based on policy elements and then uploaded them to Atlas.ti version 22 for initial coding.

Step 4: Distill your findings

The summary of all included documents is in Table 4.1. Table 3.1 presented is the summary of codes from the documents. The codes combined with the analysis for the second method of data collection.

Table 3.1

Summary of codes from document review

Policy Actors	Context	Content	Process
Information dissemination and FAQs are mostly for CDDs	Mentioned statistics of potential beneficiaries (CDDs)	Updated and aligned to existing laws	Numerous information dissemination posts during launch
Formal policy documents are mainly for interested HCI		Presence of list of FAQs in the Filipino language	Consideration given during the pandemic
		Presence of visual information	Lack of information dissemination
		Organized step by step processes	targeted to interested HCI

Focus Group Discussions

For the FGD, the identified policy actors were

1. rehabilitation professionals (OT practitioner, PT practitioner, SLP practitioner, rehabilitation medicine specialist/ developmental pediatrician);
2. administrators from public and private HCIs;
3. professional organizations of the service providers involved; and
4. parents of CDDs

The study used non-probability purposive sampling. Moreover, FGD participants must:

1. be aware of PhilHealth
2. be willing to be interviewed
3. assume the roles of the identified policy actors who may be associated with contracted HCI or potential HCIs

Invitations were sent via email to professionals, administrators, and professional organizations, while a poster with the Google Form was uploaded on Facebook on the first week of August for CDDs' parents. In the second week of August, facilitated are the follow-up emails and reposting of posters. After confirmation of willing participants, FGD with each cohort of rehabilitation professionals, administrators, professional organization representatives, and parents of CDDs was scheduled on August 24, 27, 29, and 31, respectively. The FGDs were conducted via Zoom and lasted around 100-120 minutes.

The FGD General questions are summarized in Table 3.2. The specific probing questions for each cohort and the Filipino (Tagalog) version of the questionnaire are presented in Table 3.3 and Appendix E, respectively. Three

experts, such as a rehabilitation professional specializing in Public Health (Health Administration), a rehabilitation professional specializing in Family Life and Child Development, and a Ph.D. student of Disability Studies, validated the questions. Questions were pilot tested to the first cohort group, as well as the conduct of FGD. Afterward, there were no significant revisions relayed.

Table 3.2

General questions used in the FGD

-
1. How did you know about this Z benefit package for CDDs?
 2. In the country's health system and status, how impactful is the Z benefit package?
 3. In your current role, what do you think are your roles and responsibilities in the implementation of the Z benefit package for CDDs?
 4. What are your thoughts on the package in terms of content?
 5. What are your thoughts on the package in terms of process?
 6. What do you think are the factors that hinder effective implementation of this policy?
 7. What do you think are the factors that facilitate effective implementation of this policy?
 8. What are your recommendations/suggestions to improve implementation of the Z Benefit package for CDDs?
-

Table 3.3*Specific questions for FGD cohorts*

Cohorts	With experience in implementation of the Z benefit package for CDDs	Without experience in implementation of the Z benefit package for CDDs
Managerial and administration heads of HCI offering rehabilitation services for CDDs	<p data-bbox="475 533 979 683">What are your preparations in order to participate in the Z benefit package for CDDs?</p> <p data-bbox="475 757 979 898">What are the adjustments that you made to participate in this Z benefit package for CDDs?</p> <p data-bbox="475 972 979 1122">How does this policy scheme align with the mission/vision of your institution?</p>	<p data-bbox="979 533 1361 786">What do you think about the requirements and the feasibility of your institution to be accredited for this policy scheme?</p> <p data-bbox="979 860 1361 1055">What kind of adjustments are you willing to make in order to participate in this policy?</p> <p data-bbox="979 1128 1361 1323">How does this policy scheme align with the mission/vision of your institution?</p> <p data-bbox="979 1397 1361 1727">Do you think it is possible for your institution to apply for accreditation with PhilHealth for this Z benefit package? Why or why not?</p>
Health Professionals	<p data-bbox="475 1742 979 1892">How did the implementation of this policy scheme affect your work as a health professional?</p> <p data-bbox="475 1966 979 2009">Based on your clinical expertise,</p>	<p data-bbox="979 1742 1361 1944">How do you think your work will be affected if your organization participates in this policy?</p>

	<p>what are your thoughts on the required resources stipulated in the eligibility criteria for the accreditation of HCI?</p>	<p>Based on your clinical expertise, what are your thoughts on the required resources stipulated in the eligibility criteria for the accreditation of HCI?</p>
<p>Professional Organization Representatives</p>	<p>How was your involvement during the formulation of this policy?</p> <p>How do you participate in the implementation of this policy?</p> <p>How does this policy scheme align with the mission/vision of your organization?</p>	<p>How do you think can your organization be involved in this policy scheme?</p> <p>How does this policy scheme align with the mission/vision of your organization?</p>
<p>Parents of CDDs</p>	<p>How was your experience in using the Z benefit package for CDDs?</p> <p>How did the policy scheme affect your child with developmental disability?</p> <p>What can be improved in the Z benefit package in order to reach more CDDs and their families?</p>	<p>What is the feasibility of benefitting from this Z benefit package?</p> <p>If you are not currently benefitting from this, how do access therapy services for your child?</p>

Data Analysis

In analyzing the collected data, the study adopted the content analysis procedure by Elo and Kyngas (2008). This procedure utilized a deductive approach from which the analysis structure was operationalized and based on the policy triangle elements. The steps for analysis included: 1) preparation, 2) organizing, and 3) reporting.

1) Preparation

Before transcription, the researcher assigned pseudonyms to the participants. Aside from gender and role, there was no other personal information included. Pseudonyms were assigned by retaining the participants' initials and assigning another Filipino gender-specific name. To reflect the ethnicity of the participants, a Filipino name was used (Fazio et al., 2011). Afterward, the primary investigator transcribed each recording of the FGD. Transcriptions were rechecked for a second time and transferred to MS Excel.

2) Organizing

The study adopted the categorization matrix from Elo and Kyngas (2008) and Bengtsson (2016). The researcher organized transcripts in the MS Excel sheet for deductive coding through the following steps: 1.) Identified meaning units per line for open coding; 2.) Created a condensed meaning unit; 3.) Identified codes for all meaning units; 4.) Grouped and assigned codes with similar ideas to sub-categories. Policy elements were the identified main categories. Categories, such as facilitator and barrier, were classified into themes.

For the integration of analyses from the document review and FGD, the researcher combined initial codes from the document review in Table 3.1 with the codes created in the FGD. Then, included in the paper's Appendices is a summary of the FGD and document review codes. Some codes can not classify as either a facilitator or barriers. These codes were mainly for specific recommendations that can be applied to future policy reform but were not observed yet in the current policy implementation. Furthermore, incorporated in Chapter 5 is a summary of recommendations.

Table 3.4

Categorization matrix (Sample from the FGD with Parents of CDD)

Line #	Meaning unit	Condensed meaning unit	Code	Sub-category	Category (Actor, Content, Context, Process)	Themes (Facilitator, Barrier)
22	For me, the pricing of the services is too low.	Pricing of services too low.	Inadequate costing of services	Inadequate costing of services	Content	Barrier
	It's very hard to invite professionals to volunteer themselves to be accredited in the Z package.	Professionals will be hesitant to subcontract.	Preference in private sector employment	Issues in employment	Context	Barrier

3) Reporting

All codes and categories were transferred to Atlas.ti version 22 for finalizing categorization and theming. The summary of all identified facilitators and barriers was summarized in a figure and will be presented in Chapter 4.

Rigor and Trustworthiness

To ensure rigor and trustworthiness, during the analysis, the four-dimension criteria (i.e., credibility, conformability, dependability, and transferability) were applied (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Elo et al., 2014). For credibility, the researcher rechecked codes, categories, and transcript themes. After this, initial codes from the document review were combined and followed by a re-organization of categories and themes. For member checking, participants of FGD reviewed the tabulated summary of identified facilitators and barriers. For conformability, the researcher facilitated another round of revisions for data triangulation with research memos and policy documents, while the participants' voices were reflected through direct quotations to represent the information accurately. Then, the researcher conducted a peer debriefing with the thesis supervisor to gain critical views and minimize biases and performed an audit trail by noting each step done in data collection and analysis for dependability (See Figure 3). For transferability, the variety of participants using purposeful sampling mirrors the reality of a multi-disciplinary approach in policy analysis.

Figure 3. Audit trail of data collection and analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Ensuring compliance with the ethical standards, the researcher distributed the informed consent form in pdf, which includes explicit statements on the background, purpose, procedure, voluntary participation, benefits and risk, and data management, to all participants before conducting FGDs. The FGDs were facilitated and recorded through Zoom, an encrypted video-conferencing platform. Participants' information and inputs were encoded in password-protected documents and devices. Participants were assigned pseudonyms for anonymity, wherein the first letter of the name was retained and assigned with another Filipino gender-specific name to reflect the ethnicity of the participants (Fazio et al., 2011). Participants were also invited for member checking for the accuracy of the results. Cash vouchers amounting to 200 Philippine pesos were given to the participants and will permit them to access the study upon completion.

The study protocol was reviewed and granted an exemption by the UP Manila Research Ethics board last July 8, 2022. Amendment to the informed consent forms was submitted and approved last August 1, 2022 (see Appendix H: Certificate of Exemption from UP Manila Research Ethics Board).

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

A total of 22 documents composed of seven policy documents, three policy frequently asked questions (FAQs), six reports, and six social media posts underwent a review and summarized in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1

List of documents reviewed for the policy analysis

Document Type	Title	Author	Date Published	Purpose
Policy document (n=7)	PhilHealth Circular No. 2012-0054: Manual of Procedure of the New Accreditation Process	PhilHealth	2012	To outline procedure needed to be a PhilHealth-accredited facility including the steps, fees, forms and sample letters in accordance with RA 10606 National Health Insurance Act (PhilHealth, 2012b)
	PhilHealth Circular 2015-035: Guiding Principles of the Z benefits	PhilHealth	2015	To establish the guiding principles behind all Z benefits (PhilHealth, 2015a)

PhilHealth Circular 2015-0014: Guidelines for Contracting of HCIs as Z Benefit Package Providers	PhilHealth	2015	To provide guidelines for contracting HCIs for Process for specific Z benefit packages (PhilHealth, 2015b)
PhilHealth Circular 2017-0017: Strengthening the Implementation of the No Balance Billing Policy	PhilHealth	2017	Related policy to be adhered based on the revised guiding principles of the Z benefits (PhilHealth 20121-022) emphasizing that out-of- pocket payment from PhilHealth members to HCIs are not allowed (PhilHealth, 2017)
PhilHealth Circular 2017-0029: Z Benefits for Children with Developmental Disabilities	PhilHealth	2018	Main policy document about the Z benefits for CDDs outlining pre- authorization; contracting process, minimum standards of care; availment of the benefits; monitoring and policy review; and marketing, promotion and patient empowerment (PhilHealth, 2018b)
PhilHealth Circular 2021-0022: The Guiding Principles of the Z Benefits (Revision 1)	PhilHealth	2021	To establish the guiding principles of Z benefits and to define the policies and procedure in the delivery of quality health services to

				all members (PhilHealth, 2021b)
	PhilHealth Circular No. 2022-0012: Contracting of a Health Facility as a Z Benefit Provider (Revision 1)	PhilHealth	2022	To update the process of contracting health facility for Z benefit providers emphasizing commitment of PhilHealth to contract with public tertiary hospitals and capable private HCIs (PhilHealth, 2022b)
FAQs (n=3)	Tamang Sagot_PhilHealth Circular 2015-0014 Guidelines for Contracting of HCIs as Z Benefit Package Providers	PhilHealth	2015	To provide a list of frequently asked questions answered in Filipino language for guidelines on contracting HCIs for specific Z benefit packages (PhilHealth, 2015c)
	Tamang Sagot_PhilHealth Circular No. 2017-0029 Z Benefits for Children with Developmental Disabilities	PhilHealth	2018	To provide a list of frequently asked questions answered in Filipino language about the Z benefits for CDDs (PhilHealth, 2018c)

	Tamang Sagot_PhilHealth Circular 2021-0022: The Guiding Principles of the Z Benefits (Revision 1)	PhilHealth	2021	To provide a list of frequently asked questions in Filipino language about the update guiding principles of the Z benefits (PhilHealth, 2021c)
Report (n=6)	PhilHealth Introduces Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities	PhilHealth	2018	To disseminate information on launching of the package (PhilHealth, 2018a)
	Guide to PhilHealth's Z Benefit Packages for Kids with Disabilities	Jillian E. Castillo (Smart Parenting)	2018	To disseminate information on launching of the package (Castillo, 2018)
	PhilHealth opens benefit package for children with disabilities	Futch Anthony Inso (Cebu Daily News)	2018	To disseminate information on launching of the package (Inso, 2018)
	PhilHealth launches package for disabled kids	Tina G. Santos (Philippine Daily Inquirer)	2018	To disseminate information on launching of the package (Santos, 2018)
	Extension of Validity of Approved Pre- Authorization Applications for the Z Benefits and the Outpatient Benefit for the Secondary	PhilHealth	2021	To disseminate information on extension of approved pre-authorization applications in consideration of COVID-19 pandemic (PhilHealth, 2021a)

	Prevention of Rheumatic Fever/Rheumatic Heart Disease			
	Contracted Health Facility for Z-Benefit Package as of June 30, 2022	PhilHealth	2022	To disseminate information on the updated list of contracted HCIs (PhilHealth, 2022a)
Social media post (n=6)	Celebrating awareness, rights and inclusion of children with developmental disabilities	Josephine Bundoc (Facebook)	2017	To announce successful policy development consultation together stakeholders, UNICEF, and Physicians for Peace (Bundoc, 2017)
	PhilHealth introduces Z benefit package for children with developmental disabilities	PhilHealth (Facebook)	2018	To disseminate information on launching of the package (PhilHealth, 2018b)
	PhilHealth offers package for children with disabilities	Flying Ketchup (Facebook)	2018	To disseminate information on launching of the package (Flying Ketchup, 2018)
	MOA Signing between PhilHealth and UP-PGH	PhilHealth (Facebook)	2019	To disseminate information on successful contracting of the first HCI to offer Z benefit package (PhilHealth, 2019)
	Z benefits for Children with Developmental Disabilities	BrigadaTV (Twitter)	2020	To disseminate information on launching of the package (BrigadaTV, 2020)

	PhilHealth Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities	PhilHealth (Facebook)	2020	To disseminate information on availability of the package in two contracted hospitals in NCR and Region 11 (PhilHealth, 2020)
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A total of four group discussions were held last August 2022. A one-on-one interview with a private hospital administrator was held separately due to a conflict in the schedule, then insisted on attending to another set schedule.

The policy actors, such as three rehabilitation professionals, five HCI administrators, five representatives of professional organizations, and three parents of CDDs, participated in the FGDs. More than half (9/16 [56.25%]) of participants were female. Only three (18.75%) participants were involved during policy formulation, while five (31.25%) were directly involved in the policy implementation. Developmental pediatricians and their professional society and recipients of the package from contracted HCI were contacted and followed up several times but did not participate for reasons such as rejection of invitation, unavailability, and non-response. Table 4.2 shows the demographic profile of the participants.

Table 4.2*Demographic profile of participants*

Focus Groups (n=4)	Pseudonyms (n=16)	Gender (7M:9F)	Role	Involvement with Policy	
				Formulation (p'=3/16)	Implementation (p'=5/16)
Rehabilitation Professionals	Corazon	Female	PT practitioner in private clinics	No	No
	Irina	Female	SLP practitioner in contracted public hospital	No	Yes
Administrators	Jocelyn	Female	OT practitioner in contracted public hospital	No	Yes
	Cedric	Male	Owner and manager of private for-profit therapy center and OT practitioner	No	No
	Eugene	Male	Department head and Rehabilitation Medicine specialist in contracted public hospital	No	Yes
	Jose	Male	Chief Physical Therapist in contracted public hospital	No	Yes
	Roberto	Male	Department head and PT practitioner in private hospital	No	No
	Gilda	Female	Executive director of private non-profit therapy center	No	No

Representatives from	Dona	Female	SLP board member and SLP consultant in contracted public hospital	No	Yes
Professionals	Melvin	Male	SLP board member	No	No
Organizations	Francia	Female	SLP board member	Yes	No
	Mariano	Male	PT board member	Yes	No
	Susan	Female	OT board member	No	No
Parents of CDDs	Jethro	Male	Father, Parent advocate in local PWD organization for CDDs	No	No
	Josephine	Female	Mother, Parent advocate in national PWD organization for CDDs	Yes	No
	Juanita	Female	Mother	No	No

Factors influencing the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs

Discussed in this section were the factors influencing the disability benefits package for CDDs following each of the policy elements in the triangle framework, starting with context, policy actors, content, then process. Then presented the identified facilitators and the barriers for each.

Context

In terms of context, identified the macro-contextual factors that necessitated the development of the Z benefit package, the socio-economic context of beneficiaries, governance, and laws and issues encompassing the nation.

Facilitators

The PhilHealth Circular 2017-0029 highlighted the campaign for early intervention and access to therapy sessions, which may potentially benefit the estimated 2 million CDDs. All participants in the FGD support this advocacy and are hopeful of its realization once the policy is implemented. Parents of CDD added that aside from relief from financial burden and impact on child's development, access to these services may provide relief and help them have better family dynamics.

"It's not only for the children, it's also for the family. It's a relief for the parents. It is because when you are aware of what you are dealing with, it's not as difficult. Broken marriages leading to broken families can happen when the situation of the child is too difficult to handle. I think that's also one of the

benefits - to have a more peaceful and a more understanding home.” - Josephine, parent of three CDDs.”

The PhilHealth Circular 2021-022 stipulated that the policy is updated to align provisions on RA 11032: Ease of Doing Business Act and RA 11223: Universal Healthcare Act. RA 11032, regarded as the Anti-Red Tape Act, aims to “promote integrity, accountability, proper management of public affairs and public property as well as to establish effective practices aimed at efficient turnaround of the delivery of government services and the prevention of graft and corruption in government.” Thus, the PhilHealth Circular 2022-0012 streamlined the step-by-step processes of filing for claims reimbursement for all Z benefits packages for easier preparation and transaction. On the other hand, RA 11223 was emphasized to strengthen the commitment to promoting health and widening access to services to those in need while decreasing the financial burden of all Filipino citizens. This is further supported by RA 11228: An Act Providing For The Mandatory PhilHealth Coverage for All Persons with Disability (PWDs) which indicates that all PWDs, including the CDDs, are automatically enrolled in PhilHealth and that the government pays for their premium contributions. Furthermore, the “No Balance Billing Policy” of the RA 10606 National Health Insurance Act is applied to the disability benefits package for CDDs as well. No balance billing means qualified members of PhilHealth, such as CDDs, shall not be forced to pay out-of-pocket expenses for services needed for the interventions entailed in the packages.

The policy actors who participated in the FGDs agreed that these laws are helpful as they protect the rights of CDDs to health and access to services. Moreover, the representatives from the professional organization of speech

therapists highlighted the importance of laws in providing opportunities for service providers. Case in point, the passing of RA 11249: Speech-Language Pathology Act paves the way for the creation of the licensure examination as a credible assessment for competence and compliance to national and global standards. With this, the opening of more plantilla items for SLP and promotion to higher ranks may be attained. Francia, a representative from SLP professional organization explains, *“So with SLP, because of the lack of boards, the highest rank is SLP 2. Now that there is already a board exam, we can ask for higher ranks.”* In the case of parents of CDDs, they are being more hopeful for the presence of legislative presentation in congress through a PWD party list.

Barriers

While all participants in the FGD were hopeful for the potentially significant impact of the package, they were aware of its low impact as of present due to limited access to therapy services in most provinces. Susan, a representative from OT professional organization, stressed, *“I believe the impact is low given that many institutions are not yet accredited. For example, in region 10, there are no contracted hospitals for the Z benefit package for CDDs yet. This is the whole of Northern Mindanao.”* Jethro, a parent and advocate of LGU-run disabled people organization for CDD, also raised the same sentiments, *“I’m from NCR and there are two contracted hospitals here. Among the co-parents within our group, no one was able to access this package yet. How much more in the provinces?”*

Parents who participated in the FGD shared the struggle of caring for a CDD. Jethro pointed out that regardless of socioeconomic status - all parents are challenged:

“If you are an ordinary family and the parents are minimum wage earners, therapy services will really be hard to avail. Even if the family is quite well off, it is quite costly and it entails a lot of sacrifices.”

Participants also identified political and governance issues in the country hindering policy implementation. With politics, Corazon (PT, private clinic) and Irina (SLP, contracted public hospital) pointed out that corruption-related issues with PhilHealth affect the openness of private institutions to be involved. However, Irina explained that regardless of the corruption issues, she assured that the public hospital will be supported. With governance, Juanita (parent and advocate, national disabled people organization for CDDs) stressed how implementation issues are observed not only with the Z benefit package but among most laws or policies in the country. Juanita pointed out that despite BP 344: Accessibility Law has been long implemented in 1983, most buildings are not disability-friendly until now. She also raised the issue of the absence of developmental disabilities among the categories of PWD ID as mandated in RA 7277 Magna Carta for PWD. She reported, *“For instance, for children with autism spectrum disorder, since there is no existing category for developmental disability, they are categorized as learning disability, intellectual disability, mental disorder, etc.”* With the automatic enrolment of PWDs as PhilHealth members, she cited the issue on the registry, *“We also need to fix the*

process of getting PWD IDs. Right now, the basis is the PWD DOH registry. However, there are instances that PWDs registered in the LGU could not be found in the PWD DOH registry.” On the part of the delivery mechanism of the package, Irina raised the issue of the redundancy of having a package in public hospitals that offer free or subsidized therapy services already. She explained how the social welfare services are classified from A to C as those who receive partial subsidy while those in class D or those regarded as indigent receive a full subsidy.

Next, issues related to the employment of professionals hinder the full implementation of the package. Irina shared that there are limited plantilla items in public hospitals for rehabilitation professionals. She elaborated:

“There is only one SLP [in our institution]. Opening plantilla positions can be tricky. If they were to open a position, it has to be filled within three months. If no one applies, hiring will be closed regardless.”

Jocelyn (OT, contracted public hospital) disclosed, *“Our main concern is the number of therapists. We have 11 therapists at the moment but we need a team of 20 OT staff members to open more slots for the Z package.”* The low supply of rehabilitation professionals compared to the demand is pointed out by Gilda (administrator, private non-profit institution), *“Our onsite waitlist for speech therapy is around 100 even when we already have 10 speech therapists on board. We also have a waitlist of 60 for OT, even if we already have a team of 25 OT clinicians.”* Although other groups did not mention it, it was discussed during the FGD with parents the opening of the current issue of brain drain. Jethro shared that his child's previous therapists moved overseas already. He said that he understood their situation and expressed, *“We*

have very limited professionals. And, most of them are going abroad for greener pastures. They also need to feel valued by the government.”

Ultimately, the barrier mentioned by those contracted service providers is the disruption due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Jocelyn and Dona (SLP in contracted public hospital and representative from SLP professional organization), both work at public hospitals in NCR and Davao, respectively, shared that the implementation was paused because of the physical restrictions. Dona added:

“Right now, the impact is not yet that significant as it is only in its piloting stages. Just when the program had just started, COVID-19 hit us. Hopefully, the program in our hospital will resume soon. As of now, there is only little impact.”

Policy Actors

In terms of policy actors, the policy documents included explicit roles and responsibilities of 1) interested HCI administrators to prepare for the necessary processes to be a contracted provider for the Z benefit package for CDDs 2) rehabilitation professionals (OT, SLP, PT, and rehabilitation medicine specialist/developmental pediatrician) as direct service providers and 3) CDDs who are the direct beneficiaries who are aged 0 to 17 years old and 364 days and 4) PhilHealth Z benefit coordinator who shall act as the liaison officer during implementation stage with PhilHealth.

In the FGDs, administrators, rehabilitation professionals, representatives from professional organizations, and parents of CDDs gave their perspectives on how people influence policy implementation.

Facilitators

During policy formulation, representatives from professional organizations and parent advocate recalled their involvement in the consultations organized by PhilHealth. Mariano, a representative from the PT organization, Francia, a representative from the SLP organization, and Juanita attended the said meetings. Susan, a representative from the OT organization, did not participate during this period but made sure that an OT representative was present during the consultation meetings. Mariano shared that the focus of their inputs was mainly on the required resources. On the other hand, Josephine raised concerns and struggles of parents of CDDs and emphasized the potential impact of the existence of this package in alleviating the burden among families. During the contracting process, Jocelyn, Irina, Jose (an administrator and PT who contracted a public hospital), and Dona was involved in helping acquire the required resources by PhilHealth.

Participants affiliated with the public sector highlighted their advantage in terms of administrative support. Contracted HCI received strong support from higher management and has an in-house PhilHealth coordinator. Eugene, a rehabilitation medicine specialist and administrator in a contracted public hospital, reported, “We were tasked by the medical director to prepare the institution through reviewing the policy documents and acquiring needed resources to be a contracted facility.” He further elaborated that participating in this kind of package can be seen as a form of

investment, such that services are free for the CDDs, but the hospital services are reimbursed through PhilHealth. Jocelyn also raised that by working in the government, she and her team, who were accustomed to the administrative functions (i.e., filling out forms and coordinating with PhilHealth staff), were involved in package implementation. She explained that even with the package, her work as an occupational therapist is still the same, just that there were different forms to fill out for those CDDs to be enrolled under the Z benefit package.

All HCI administrators, rehabilitation professionals, and representatives from professional organizations expressed their willingness to participate in the implementation of the package. As HCI administrators in the non-contracted private institutions like Gilda, Roberto (head in the private tertiary hospital), and Cedric (head and OT in private therapy center) shared that equitability in service provision is part of the values in their institutions. Corazon also agreed that, as a rehabilitation professional in a private clinic, she is willing to extend her services to potential package beneficiaries. Mariano and Francia also highlighted the roles of the professional organization in having a proactive role in negotiations during policy reformation and re-evaluation of the equitability of access. Mariano suggested that advocating for the Z benefit package for CDDs is an opportunity for professional organizations and other sectors to collaborate and unite in the shared advocacy.

Barriers

There were organizations reportedly involved during policy formulation, but potential service providers, such as administrators and pediatric rehabilitation

professionals who participated in FGD, were not involved. Eugene shared his sentiments, *“When they were creating this policy, not all of the people who will be involved in this package were invited. The PhilHealth was not able to ask all relevant stakeholders in creating this package.”* Despite the intention stated in the policy to affiliate with interested and capable HCIs, Francia said that during the consultation in 2017, contracting tertiary public hospitals was the focus and that there were no guidelines or standards published about the process of how free-standing clinics, such as therapy centers, may participate.

Next, human resource issues also emerged during the discussion. Cedric and Roberto, as both heads of private institutions, shared that they do not have a PhilHealth Z benefit coordinator. If ever they are contracted, they might assign one of their staff to have this additional role. Roberto explained, *“Our existing staff may act as a coordinator if PhilHealth will allow that. We still need to review if there will be numerous CDDs availing the package before we can request additional manpower.”* Rehabilitation professionals and administrators also pointed out the small number of full-time professionals compared to part-time professionals in the hospital and centers, thus having limited functions in planning and preparing for contracting with the Z benefit package for CDDs. Irina and Melvin, representatives from the SLP organization, who both experienced working in private and public institutions, expressed that the preference of SLPs and other professionals is mainly due to the better remuneration in the private sector. On the other hand, Francia offered a perspective that the assigned policy actors responsible for facilitating the process during policy formulation leave during the implementation stage. The reason for

policies not being implemented well is maybe the leadership turnover in agencies and organizations.

During the FGD with parents, it was raised that the disability sectors receive help whose main focus is allowance instead of services. Jethro as a parent advocate in their local PWD organization argued:

We will continue collaboration with the LGU and federations. Especially now that the focus in the disability sector is allowance. For me, what would I do with the money, say Php 1000? How much does therapy cost? That will only do for one session and the transportation fees.

Content

In terms of content: features of the package in terms of presentation of information, services, costing, required resources, and overall completeness of necessary information about the Z benefit package were focused on during the discussion and were observed in the document review.

Facilitators

During the FGD, all participants appreciated the existence of the policy. Although there were no specific factors noted, they agreed that the content is generally comprehensive and complete with the list of services and rates in the main policy document PhilHealth Circular 2017-0029. There was also a published compilation of frequently asked questions for policy documents written in the Filipino

language, specifically Tagalog. The information was organized in numbered sections and presented through visual information strategically designed for those who will view it. Summary tables, flowcharts, forms, and sample letters are included in the annexes of the policy documents.

Barriers

The inadequate cost of services was pointed out unanimously across the groups. All were agreeable to the justified rates given to the initial and discharge assessment by the medical doctors but deemed that the assigned fees for the services provided by the rehabilitation professionals were insufficient. Cedric explained:

The assessment fees will not compensate the therapists, who may earn 450-550 per hour during therapy sessions, and twice the amount for assessment fees because of the extra work to make the document. The allied health professional is really at a disadvantage.

He further noted that the allotted fees by PhilHealth for the set of therapy sessions will only cover the therapist's professional fee, but not that of the clinic's cut for the service provided. Thus, it will not be sustainable for the business.

The second concern is about the required resources. The rehabilitation professionals were surprised that the materials, such as the toys needed, were not specified. Corazon argued, *"There are some things which aren't needed while there were which should have been specified such as vestibule, sensory equipment,*

trampoline, tilt board, benches, chairs, etc. which are necessary for PT sessions.”

Corazon also observed that some materials like sphygmomanometer, ultrasound, and paraffin baths are not needed and may be more appropriate for adult practice. Irina and Melvin noticed the lack of feeding tools in the required resources. Melvin reasoned that this might be rooted in the deficiencies in specific descriptors on the service indications. He expressed:

I'm not sure if it would be wise to add more specificities, like if the child has speech and communication problems. For example, the problem is voice or in feeding and swallowing. To what extent can we involve specific conditions based on the definitions in the documents?

Furthermore, rehabilitation professionals, administrators, and professional organization representatives brought up the limited scope of assessment tools required in terms of developmental domains, indications, and cultural validity. Corazon pointed out that the required assessment tool for PT, which is the GMFM (Gross Motor Function Measure), is only indicated for children with cerebral palsy and is not appropriate for other developmental disabilities. Cedric also had the same sentiments, *“Assuming, for example, we acquired the Beery VMI which is for school-aged children. What if we have a 2-year-old client, is he not qualified for Beery? I can't use the Z package.”* Jocelyn shared a specific experience and narrated:

I remember when procurement for the other assessment tools was still ongoing, we had to use an inappropriate standardized assessment tool. Inappropriate in the sense that the child does not have the skills yet to perform the tasks

Aside from the limitations due to indications because of age and conditions, rehabilitation professionals also noted how these required assessment tools are not entirely culturally valid as these are based on Western norms and are in the English language.

Lastly, some participants pointed out the absence of certain protocols, which signals that the policy needs to be revised. There seems to be a lack of protocol for specialized treatment sessions. Melvin was wondering what the implications are on sessions and fees if a certain SLP intervention would need a certain number of sessions and a certain level of training from the provider. On the other hand, Susan pointed out that there was a lack of protocol for the accreditation of rehabilitation professionals aside from the requirement to have a license or certificate from the accredited professional organization. The accreditation for professionals indicated on the website was only for physicians, nurses, dentists, and midwives. Moreover, Corazon, Mariano, and Francia raised concerns about adding COVID-19 protocols for the policy to be adaptive and responsive to the context.

Process

In terms of the process, this refers mechanism that involves the stakeholders and the overall implementation of the policy. As stipulated in policy documents, implementation of the Z benefit package for CDDs starts with the accreditation of the facility by PhilHealth (PhilHealth Circular 2012-0054), contracting to be a Z benefit provider (PhilHealth Circulars 2021-0022 and 2022-0012), and providing the services for CDDs (PhilHealth Circular 2017-0029). Across the policy documents, PhilHealth

also mentioned the inclusion of marketing and evaluation, and monitoring through policy review.

Participants shared their observations and experiences on the processes such as information dissemination, subcontracting, stakeholder engagement activities, quality assurance, and service delivery.

Facilitators

During the official launch of the package in 2018, numerous information dissemination reports were released in various media. The summary of evidence of information dissemination efforts is presented in Table 4.1. Most participants across the FGDs were familiar with the disability benefits package for CDDs. Several parents of CDDs, disability groups, professional organizations, and rehabilitation professionals reached the information dissemination posts based on the comments and shares in the social media posts.

The next factor appreciated across all groups was the option to subcontract private professionals via the contracted HCI, which could provide multi-disciplinary services despite the lack of a full-time employed set of rehabilitation professionals. Even with the parents of CDDs' lens, Juanita mentioned, *"Maybe if the government will subcontract for this package, it will be feasible. I think the professionals will not be able to give their whole week because the salary is not competitive."*

Equally important, implicitly indicated in the series of policy documents, was quality assurance on the policy implementation, which the interested HCIs can review. Participants working in the public sector, like Irina and Eugene, stressed the

importance of accreditation and contracting standards as these processes stand for accountability and corruption-free implementation. Francia highlighted the clauses for policy review and the importance of evaluation and monitoring to see what is being done. According to the PhilHealth Circular 2021-0022, conducting policy reviews regularly between one and three years shall be.

Lastly, the extension of validity of approved pre-authorization applications was one of the collected reports in the document review. For those enrolled in the Z benefit package for CDDs, the approved pre-authorization applications from March 17, 2020, to September 12, 2021, were extended for one (1) fiscal year and 180 calendar days.

Barriers

Included with those who reached the initial information dissemination efforts, participants raised issues regarding their information dissemination process. With the information dissemination reports from the document review, especially on posts via social media, people were hopeful and happy with the package's existence, but there were many unanswered questions on how to avail of the package. During the initial launch, there was a failure to mention that there was still a lack of contracted HCI in 2018. It was only in a Facebook post by PhilHealth last December 2020 that the package is only available in two tertiary public hospitals in NCR and Davao. All 12 information dissemination reports included in the study were specifically for the parents of CDDs. There was a lack of information dissemination efforts via the official website, newspapers, and social media focused on inviting potential service providers for CDDs who want to partner with PhilHealth.

Another identified barrier was the lack of stakeholder engagement activities from PhilHealth staff. The lack of visits from capable service providers in the private sector hinders the possibility of having more partners for the Z package. Cedric expressed that other government offices, like the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR), hold visits and wondered if PhilHealth could do the same. He explained:

If PhilHealth wants this initiative (to be known), they will go to clinics and spread the "Oh Sir, can you please join this program?" There's a bigger chance for clinics to get involved if PhilHealth is stepping up and asking for partnerships. Corazon also provided a similar perspective,

I think that would be easier. PhilHealth will be the one to communicate [with therapy clinics]. Don't they have PhilHealth staff to do this? They can go to the centers and have a census of potential service providers. If there's a requirement, they can readily ask [the clinic administrator] to fill out forms.

In contrast, since tertiary hospitals were the primary targets, participants from contracted public hospitals disclosed that PhilHealth invited them by sending the needed documents and forms. However, there was a lack of formal orientation sessions on the contracting and implementation process. Corazon, Irina, Jose, and Eugene shared that they navigated themselves through reading the policy documents and intermittently asking questions from the PhilHealth coordinator in their hospitals.

On the other hand, Roberto recalled that PhilHealth staff visited their private hospital and introduced the package with the necessary documents. However, there was a lack of submission status follow-up, and there was no opportunity to clarify

questions on contracting after submitting the needed forms for the self-assessment.

Gilda also shared the same experience:

There was a time when I was invited to be part of a meeting [with a contracted public hospital and their partner university) and one of the agendas is to subcontract and engage private therapy clinics to be providers of the services. However, there was no follow-up after the meeting.

Although stipulated in the PhilHealth Circulars 2017-0029, 2021-022, and 2022-0012 that policy review, as part of monitoring and evaluation, shall be conducted every three years, none of the FGD participants received invitations. There were no uploaded policy documents about revisions to the Z benefit package for CDDs.

Another theme of barriers is the tediousness of the processes for accreditation, contracting, and filing of claims for reimbursement stipulated in PhilHealth Circulars: 2012-0054, 2017-0029, 2021-0022, and 2022-0012. Participants affiliated with the private sector expressed the inconvenience of preparing the budget for procurement, shipping equipment and tools from abroad, and additional staff training for the required standardized assessment tools. Moreover, for filing claims for reimbursement, numerous forms must be filled out by the service providers and parents of CDDs, which can impose an extra burden in terms of time for the professionals. Moreover, possible difficulties for the parents of CDDs with limited health literacy can be encountered, given that forms were mostly written in English. FGD participants also brought up anticipated delays in

reimbursing claims for service providers. Cedric, a therapy center owner, explained that it would take some time to file claims, because the process may affect the timely disbursement of the consultants' salary. In terms of the experienced implementation during service delivery, there was a limited number of sessions to merit re-evaluation before the client enrolled in another set of therapy sessions, as noted by Jocelyn and Dona. Dona explained:

For example, the patient is recommended for OT and PT twice a week and then SLP once or twice a week. The ten sessions would be all used up easily. After which, a requirement to submit an assessment so you can move on to the next cycle. You won't see much effect after two or three sessions.

Through the combination of the document review and FGDs with identified policy actors (i.e., rehabilitation professionals, HCI administrators, representatives of the professional organization, and parents of CDDs), facilitators and barriers in each of the elements (i.e., context, policy actors, content, and process) of the policy triangle. Presented in Figure 4 is the summary of the identified facilitators and barriers.

Figure 4. Summary of facilitators and barriers in the Z benefit package for CDDs.

Policy Elements	Facilitators	Barriers
Context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Campaign for early intervention and access to therapy • Increased accessibility helps families with CDDs • Alignment with existing laws • Passing of relevant laws • Presence of legislative representation in Congress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Package has low impact and reach after 4 years of launch • Financial burden felt by families across socio-economic status • Issues in politics and governance in the country • Issues related to employment of professionals • Implementation is disrupted by COVID-19 pandemic
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement during policy formulation and implementation of organizations and public sector • Administrative advantage of public sector • Alignment with values and advocacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of involvement of other potential service providers • Human resource issues • Help received in disability sector is focused on allowance instead of services
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generally comprehensive and with complete list of services and rates • Presence of a separate document containing list of frequently asked questions in the Filipino language • Organized and easy to follow policy documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate costing of services • Concerns on required resources • Absence of certain protocols
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerous information dissemination during launch • Subcontracting private professionals • Assuring quality of implementation • Extension of validity of approved pre-authorization applications as consideration due to pandemic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issues in information dissemination • Lack of stakeholder engagement activities from PhilHealth • Tediousness of processes • Limited number of sessions to merit re-evaluation

Discussion

Through policy analysis, the study determined the factors that influence the current status of the implementation of the disability benefits package for CDDs in the Philippines. The study showed that the policy is equipped with various mechanisms and supports through passing the Universal Healthcare Act and amendments to the National Health Insurance Act and the Magna Carta for PWDs. Moreover, the invited policy actors understood the significance of the policy and were hopeful that the policy implementation subject to improvement so that equity in health services for CDDs could be achieved.

While there seem to be many facilitators noted during the analysis, it was apparent how anchored the facilitators were on the foundations of legislation, promising services, and technical policy processes. On the other hand, the barriers enumerated remained an immense obstacle to the slow implementation and non-participation of potential service providers despite interest in partaking in the equitable service provision.

The influence of each policy element based on the study's findings will be discussed on how these elements affect health policies in other developing countries.

Context

In the study, it was found how the passing of laws, such as the UHC act, National Health Insurance Act, and amendments to the Magna Carta for PWD, serve as the foundation for launching the Z benefit package for CDD. In a narrative review

of countries passing the UHC act by Atim and colleagues (2021), they observed that LMICs such as Ethiopia, Ghana, Nigeria, and the Philippines passed the UHC act to align with their national health priorities. While passing the UHC act enabled developing countries to increase national health insurance coverage, the extent of coverage in benefit packages remains limited as budget resource allocation is still dependent on the country's income level. The push to have a UHC law from a political decision with vague technical analysis and financing mechanisms undermines the sustainability of the package (Atim et al., 2021).

The issue of politics and governance challenges the ability of countries to achieve equity and quality in health service delivery. In Southeast Asian and African countries, Naher et al. (2020) reported that corruption in the health sector is rampant. Corruption within the government is the cause of various financial-related problems, such as poor salaries and benefits of health professionals and increased out-of-pocket expenses, due to the preference for private HCI for a better quality of health service experience. Furthermore, circumstances like these are also related to the non-preference of health professionals to work for the government and the threat of brain drain, which poses a threat to the Z benefit package implementation for CDDs and other health services in the country. Health professionals from LMICs such as the Philippines, India, Pakistan, Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa migrate to the United States and United Kingdom due to poor remuneration, poor working environment, unstable political climate, limited career growth, and academic training (Saghir et al., 2020; Karan et al., 2016).

Policy Actors

All policy actors in the study expressed willingness to be involved and were hopeful for the successful implementation of the package. However, it was reflected in the study how policy actors in the form of organizations (i.e., representatives from professional organizations, PWD organizations) were given more agency or sense of control during the formulation of the policy. The participants who do not hold official positions in professional organizations and disability groups felt a lack of input among other potential service providers outside NCR and from the private sector. The explicit statement that PhilHealth focuses on contracting tertiary public hospitals and the lack of protocol accreditation and contracting of free-standing clinics contradict their stated openness to deal with the private sector. This centralized policy-making style, wherein PhilHealth concentrates control on specific policy actors alone, inhibits the Z benefit package for CDDs' potential to achieve equitability in access to therapy services. Centralization of policy-making may help gain momentum during formulation as fewer policy actors are involved. However, other policy actors' possible contributions and innovations are overlooked, affecting participation during the implementation stage (Scarffe et al., 2022, Liwanag and Wyss, 2018). Liwanag and Hyss (2018) also stressed that centralization fails to consider the diverse context of the indigenous and marginalized policy actors affecting service delivery. In Malawi, Nigeria, and other LMICs, local stakeholders felt they had no influence in policy-making compared to the preferred stakeholders commonly invited who are associated with specific organizations (Masefield et al., 2021; Uneke et al., 2013; Vanyoro et al., 2019).

The limitations on participation in the study's findings and related international literature demonstrate the tokenistic level of participation during policy-making. In Arnstein's ladder of participation (1969), inviting hand-picked policy actors who hold power in organizations is called placation, placed at ladder level 5. To move to the next step of the ladder, which is a partnership, means redistribution of power through negotiations between citizens and people who hold certain official positions shall be implemented.

Content

After considering the various voices of policy actors, the results of the study highlight the concept of sociomateriality - "the entanglement of social and material in everyday life" (Orlikowski, 2007, p.1). The dynamic interaction of policy elements embodies a socio-material assemblage, defined by MacLeod et al. (2019, p.178) as "a complex tangle of natural, technological, human, and non-human elements that come together to accomplish both intended and unintended outcomes." Focusing on the policy's content, rehabilitation professionals, administrators, and professional organization representatives all raised concerns about the compliance on required 'material' resources stipulated in the policy's content affecting policy actors and processes. For instance, the imposed moral conflict on policy actors in prioritizing between the code of ethics and equitability in the process of service delivery is characterized by the following circumstances: 1) using an inappropriate tool to reimburse claims on assessment fees, and 2) maintaining standing on the appropriate use of tool but only accepting clients indicated for available standardized tools in the institution. Moreover, the additional burden of procurement to interested

HCI and waiting time for importing Western-referenced resources affect the timely implementation of rehabilitation services. The preference for using standardized tests is useful for measuring outcomes. However, putting a premium on the use of these quantitative tests when a functional evaluation may be administered is influenced by biomedical standards. This is a manifestation of an ableist approach of rehabilitation professionals to measure the severity of disability which may not always be appropriate to the CDDs' goals (Yao et al., 2022).

Additionally, the mentioned lack of protocols in terms of service delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic imposes changes in the demands in terms of required resources, especially when the use of telehealth is prevalent due to the safety risks of a face-to-face delivery is a global practice already (Doraiswamy et al., 2021). The inclusion of telehealth services in the Z benefit package for CDDs may also be reflected in future amendments so that continuous service delivery may be performed in compliance with physical restrictions and consideration of safety risks.

Process

Based on the policy documents found, the Z benefit package for CDDs included clauses on quality assurance and policy review, yet there were no published reports about these undertakings even though policy reviews are stipulated every three years (PhilHealth Circular No. 2021-0022). Although information dissemination efforts were deemed effective during the launch of the Z benefit package for CDDs – giving hope to several potential beneficiaries, however, interested stakeholders who engaged with posted online publication materials on social media were not responded clearly on how and where to avail of the Z benefit package for CDDs. The lack of timely updates on policy review and issues in

information dissemination reflect the low responsiveness of the national health insurance and leave people feeling disappointed by the system of overpromising and underdelivering (Zezza and Nacinovich, 2011).

In the dominance of HCIs run by the private sector and with the preference of rehabilitation professionals to work for the private sector, strengthening partnerships with the private sector through sustainable contracting arrangements is crucial for optimal health service delivery. The presence of the partnerships, seen in the listing of Z benefit providers from the private sector, is a positive indicator of the feasibility of further cultivating collaboration. For instance, with the Z benefit for coronary artery bypass graft, 16 out of 24 (66.67%) providers are from the private sector (PhilHealth, 2022a). Factors on successful contracting with other Z benefits may pave the way for how to invite more service providers for the rehabilitation needs of CDDs.

With the discussion among policy actors from the private sector in the study, the lack of stakeholder engagement from PhilHealth, such as personal visits, and the burden of paperwork for the costing and claims reimbursement were the main hindrances on why they hesitate to apply as a contracted service provider. In a report by Mbogo et al. (2021), the social health insurance of Kenya achieved sustainable service delivery through organizing the private sector, digitization, and contracting through an intermediary. First, organizing the private sector can be done by working with professional organizations to identify qualified service providers participating in public-private endeavors. Second, through digitization, a clinic management system is installed, which supports “scheduling and patient communications, medical record documentation, billing and payments, quality assurance, inventory management, and external reporting (Mbogo et al., 2021, p.

11).” Lastly, contracting through an intermediary is similar to the process of subcontracting, wherein an accredited HCI may affiliate with private service providers by sharing a caseload of CDDs, which helps streamline the reimbursement claims process.

In this study, the policy actors from the public sector were agreeable to the standardized service fees, while those from the private sector felt that the assigned rates were a bit low compared to the current pricing in their institutions. Honda and Obse (2020) argued that these uniform rates by social health insurance systems among public and private service providers can be counterproductive and serve as a source of dissatisfaction on cost in the view of private HCIs. In Ghana, their social health insurance pays higher payment rates for their private service providers such that public service providers already receive salaries and other subsidies from the Ministry of Health. Furthermore, in Malawi and Tanzania, both the social health insurance and the local government units help fund the salaries of contracted private service providers.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

This study offers an overview of the policy elements influencing the current implementation status of the Z benefit package for CDDs using the policy triangle framework of Walt and Gilson (1994). Through document review and FGDs with contracted and potential service providers (i.e., public and private HCI administrators and professional organizations) and beneficiaries (i.e., parents of CDDs and parent advocates) – facilitators and barriers were identified.

In summary, it shows how the current context of the Philippine healthcare system is anchored through the presence of laws and policies supporting the advocacy of early intervention and access to therapy services of CDDs but hindered by issues on politics, governance, and the labor force. The policy actors (service providers and beneficiaries) are hopeful of the continuous implementation of the Z benefit package nationwide and share the advocacy for CDDs. However, the limited involvement of all potential policy actors in policy development and the limited human resources for service provision impede them. Although the policy's content is technically sound and comprehensive, concerns regarding cost and complying with needed resources hold the translation to implementation, and the lack of protocols poses an adaptability and sustainability threat.

Processes and initial dissemination efforts involved in implementation emphasize quality assurance and effectiveness during launch, respectively. However, the lack of activities to continuously engage potential service

providers and the tediousness of the overall process limit the participation of service providers from both the public and private sectors. In conclusion, while the policy seems promising during launch, the disability benefits package for CDDs remains underutilized because the identified barriers outweigh the facilitators on each policy element. Policy reform is needed to improve the implementation of the disability benefits package for CDDs.

In this policy analysis, the policy triangle framework is a helpful tool in mapping out gaps in policy implementation among different aspects: context, policy actors, content, and process. It organizes the analysis structure and enables holistic consideration through a rigorous review of policy documents and exploration of perspectives of policy actors. Identifying factors that support and hinder helps prevent policy failure. Although generalization of results is limited to the case in focus, awareness of facilitators and barriers that affect policy implementation can lead to future policy reform and formulation in other developing countries.

Recommendations

Based on the significance and findings of the study, recommendations for policy reform, education and training, and research were drawn. For the policy reform, the researcher listed specific recommendations for each policy element in Table 5. The researcher also suggests discussing these recommendations during policy review. Moreover, policy actors are encouraged to identify prioritization and strategies considering the study's results and recommendations to achieve better outcomes in terms of the equitability of the policy.

For education and training, the role of service providers and service users as policy actors in policy development is necessary to discuss in the curricula of health professions programs and through workshops/seminars with PWDs. Also, the collaborative nature of the processes involved in policy development necessitates a professional to have competencies to effectively work with people of varying backgrounds consisting of health and non-health professionals. Thus, the introduction of WHO's suggested Framework of Action on Interprofessional Education and Collaborative Practice (WHO, 2010) can be a good resource. Moreover, policy engagements should include co-designing with service users via non-intimidating approaches such as storytelling. In a literature review by Davidson (2017), storytelling as a communication strategy highlights the importance of the policy narrative, which includes first-hand stories of service users. Storytelling is a justifiable way of informing policy-making through informal sharing, photography, role-playing, charting, and cognitive mapping, among others (Davidson, 2017).

For research, more policies affecting health and disability issues in the Philippines and other countries can be investigated through the case-study design and use of the policy triangle framework for holistic policy analysis (Walt and Gilson, 1994). Because this study only included external policy actors, future studies are encouraged to involve internal policy actors, such as the Ministry of Health and national health insurance staff, for a complete representation of all concerned policy actors.

Table 5

Specific recommendations for the disability benefit package for CDDs

Policy Element	Recommendations
Context	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Laws such as the Magna Carta of PWDs must be amended to include specific category for developmental disabilities.● Update registry for PWD identification cards in the DOH registry to refrain difficulties in availing for the Z benefit package for CDDs and other benefits from PhilHealth.● Review standardization of salary of rehabilitation professionals in order to increase employment in public HCIs and decrease brain drain.
Policy Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Include more potential service providers (i.e., administrators, rehabilitation professionals) both from the public and private sector during policy engagements.● Consider including universities with rehabilitation professions program helping in human resource through internship programs for graduating students and through research endeavors.● Consider teaming up with local government in providing assistance with needs (i.e., transportation allowance) of parents and CDDs in order to access therapy services.
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Review utilization of required assessment tools. Consider using assessment tools that tests wider scope of developmental domains and are more culturally valid.● Consider creating a free standardized form for assessment with the help of experts.● Add a protocol for service delivery during the pandemic such as telehealth services.● Add a protocol on the process of accreditation of rehabilitation professionals.

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- Include updates on successful service provision and other testimonies of contracted HCIs.

Policy Element	Recommendations
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review consultation styles used during policy development and review. Adapt rights-based approach and health systems thinking in order to achieve equitability of access to services. ● Clarify information dissemination of Z benefit package to CDDs by including contracted HCIs in the publication material. ● Upload information dissemination specifically targeted to potential HCIs. ● Conduct visits to potential service providers. ● Conduct proper orientation to contracted HCIs. ● Review allotted number of sessions per type of therapy services in once cycle. Consider increasing number of sessions needed per cycle as early intervention approach recommends more frequent sessions. Thus, a CDD recommended for all OT, PT and SLP services can easily use up allotted ten sessions in a month then would be automatically subjected for a re-evaluation before he/she can receive the second cycle of therapy sessions. ● Consider incentives to contracted HCIs with Z benefit package (i.e., premium contributions, assistance to other required resources). ● Utilize subcontracting of private rehabilitation professionals by increasing contracted tertiary public hospitals as these HCIs are automatic accredited PhilHealth compared to private HCIs which may need to undergo this additional step.

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Appendix A

Recommended questions for document review adopted from Dalglish et al. (2020) and Cheung et al. (2010)

Actors	<p>Which voices are represented in the overall body of documents? Which are not?</p> <p>Are obligation of policy actors specified?</p> <p>Are the corresponding obligations of policy actors' part of their existing duties?</p>
Content	<p>How complete is the set of documents? What is missing?</p> <p>Which documents were easy to find? Which were harder to find? Which proved impossible to find? Why might this be the case?</p> <p>How do the documents compare in terms of content? How do they compare in terms of style, format, length and 'look'? How about in terms of formality and tone?</p> <p>What visual information can you find in the documents (charts and graphs, pictures, etc.)?</p> <p>Do the documents 'speak to each other'? Do they reference each other, or respond to each other's arguments or propositions? Are they responding to other documents not included in the review?</p> <p>Are goals explicitly stated?</p> <p>Are financial and human resources addressed?</p>
Context	<p>How are the same issues discussed in different ways across documents?</p> <p>How are documents similar or different across different topic areas, types of document or governance levels (e.g., global, national, sub-national)?</p> <p>How does the information from documents compare to data from other data sources (e.g., interviews, focus groups, observation, quantitative analyses)?</p> <p>What are the identified supports from other sectors?</p> <p>How is the political climate?</p> <p>How is the cooperation between public and private organizations?</p> <p>Has policy caught media's interest?</p>
Process	<p>Are there indicated monitoring and evaluation mechanisms?</p> <p>Is there a nominated committee or independent body to perform policy evaluation?</p> <p>Does a follow up take place after sufficient period to allow effects of policy change to become evident?</p>

Appendix B

Sample Email Invitation to Participants

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

[Date]

[Name of Respondent]

[Affiliation]

[Address]

Dear [Name of Respondent]:

Greetings! I am Pauline Gail V. Martinez, a Master of International Health Student in the Faculty of Management and Development Studies at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am writing to your good office to request for your research participation in my study entitled, *“Disability Benefit Package for the Children with Developmental Disabilities: A Policy Analysis.”* This study seeks to:

- 1) Describe the current context, actors, content and process of the disability benefit package for children with developmental disabilities (CDDs)
- 2) Explore perspectives of actors towards implementation of the disability benefit package and their critiques on the context, content and process of the policy
- 3) Determine the facilitators and barriers that influence the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs

I would like to invite you to participate in a 90-to-120-minute focus group discussion together with [cohort of participants] regarding rehabilitation services to CDDs – to discuss and share insights on the PhilHealth’s Z-benefit Package for CDDs. The focus group discussion will be held on **[tentative date]** via Zoom Video Communications.

I believe that your perspectives as one of the main stakeholders will be crucial for policy implementation and policy reform that may improve access of rehabilitation services to CDDs. If you have other inquiries, let me know.

I am looking forward to your positive response. Thank you very much!

Respectfully,

Noted by:

PAULINE GAIL V. MARTINEZ, DipIH, OTRP
Master of International Health Student
UP Open University
paulinegailmartinez@gmail.com / +639267081860

ASSOC. PROF. MICHAEL P. SY, PHD
Research Adviser
Affiliate Faculty, UP Open University

Appendix C
Poster for Parents of CDDs

Invitation to Participate in Research Study

If you are a parent:

- of a child with developmental disability receiving therapy services whether in public/private institutions
- who is familiar with PhilHealth
- who is willing to participate in a focus group discussion with other parents

You are invited to participate in this study entitled, **Disability Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities: A Policy Analysis**".

Scan the QR code and see more details.

SCAN ME

Appendix D

Google Form for Parents of CDDs

[Invitation to Parents] Disability Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities: A Policy Analysis

paulinegailmartinez@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

* Required

Email *

Your email

This is a required question

Introduction

I am Pauline Gail V. Martinez, a graduate student in UPOU and the investigator of this study in partial fulfillment of my Master of International Health degree. As a parent of a child with developmental disabilities, you are invited as a participant in the focus group discussion about the PhilHealth Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities (CDDs). If you have any questions/clarifications about this study, please feel free to contact me and I will be happy to answer your queries.

Purpose

This study seeks to analyze the factors that influence the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs in the Philippines.

The following specific research objectives are formulated:

- 1) Describe the current context, actors, content and process of the disability benefit package for CDDs
- 2) Explore perspectives of actors towards implementation of the disability benefit package and their critiques on the context, content and process of the policy
- 3) Determine the facilitators and barriers that influence the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs

Type of Research Intervention

To participate in this study, you will be undergoing a focus group discussion which is estimated to approximately 90 to 120 minutes. The focus group discussion will be conducted via an online video conferencing platform (i.e. Zoom Video Communications).

Participant Selection

You are selected to participate in this research because of your substantial role in your organization, profession, society or a parent of a child with developmental disability. Your perspective about this policy (Z benefit package for CDDs) will be helpful in order to identify factors that influence its current state of implementation. A total of 16 participants is expected to participate in the study which will be divided into 4 groups with 4 participants each. Once confirmed, you will be joined by other three participants in the group of the same background (i.e. managers/administrators, rehabilitation professionals, board members of professional organizations, parents of CDDs).

Voluntary Participation

As a participant, you have the right to refuse or withdraw your participation. When the focus group discussion has already begun/completed, you may request that the information you have provided not be used in the study.

Procedures

Once you have accepted participation, an email will be sent to you regarding the meeting details and schedule.

A focus group discussion will be conducted with other participants of similar background and the principal investigator via an online video conference platform. Permission to record the meeting via the video conference platform or an audio recorder will be asked. General set of questions will be sent to you after your confirmation of participation. Probing questions may be asked.

All information will be kept confidential and focus group discussion transcripts will be saved in a password-protected file and laptop. Pseudonyms will be used to maintain privacy and confidentiality. All data used in the study will be discarded one year after the study has been completed.

Duration

Aside from the 90 to 120-minute discussion, participants will be reached during the data analysis process to validate the analysis of the results. Participants will be given at least two weeks to respond and a follow-up will be given after the first week. If there are no responses given, this will be considered that the participant agrees with the initial interpretation and analysis.

Risks

There are no directed risks associated with the study. However, if the participant becomes uncomfortable, he/she may not answer a specific question or may opt to discontinue participation.

Benefits

Information about the PhilHealth Z benefit package for CDDs will be given and may spark interest of participants/institutions to participate as an accredited healthcare provider. Once the study is completed, recommendations may be used as evidence for policy reform that may lead to improvement of implementation and improvement of access to healthcare services.

Reimbursements

Participating to this study is voluntary, thus no corresponding compensation will be given. However, participants are entitled to receive reimbursement for expenses (i.e. internet data) incurred as a result of their participation. Token of appreciation such as food vouchers will also be provided amounting to P200.00.

Confidentiality

All information provided will be treated as confidential. Pseudonyms will be assigned to participants. Only role and type of sector (for professionals involved) shall be associated with the direct quotations in the process of reporting results of the study.

Sharing the results

Once the study has been completed, the participants will be informed and key findings will be shared via email. A copy of the full manuscript may also be given as requested.

Right to refuse or withdraw

It is emphasized that participants have the right to refuse and withdraw from the study at any time.

Data Management

Focus group discussion transcripts will be saved in a Word document in a password protected file and laptop. The raw data will be available to the principal investigator and the research adviser only. All data from the study will be discarded, one year after the study has been completed.

Who to Contact

For further information and questions, you may contact:

Dr. Michael P. Sy
Adviser | Principal Investigator
mpsy@up.edu.ph/ +6395600256627

The study has been approved by the UPM Research Ethics Board (UPM REB) and may be reached through the following contact for information regarding the rights of study participants, including grievances and complaints.

Dr. Cecilia Jimeno
Address: Room 126, Ground Floor
National Institutes of Health, UP Manila
623 Pedro Gil St.
Ermita 1000 Manila
Email: upmreb@post.upm.edu.ph
Tel: +63 2 8526-4346

Do you consent to participate in the study? *

- Yes
 No

Next

Page 1 of 2

Clear form

Demographics of the Participant

Name of Participant *

Your answer

Email *

Your answer

Contact Number *

Your answer

Target date for FGD via Zoom is on August 31 (Wed), 6pm. Are you available? *

Yes

No

Is your child with developmental disability currently receiving therapy services? *

Yes

No

What kind of rehabilitation or therapy service/s does your child receive? Check all * that applies.

Developmental pediatrician assessment

Occupational therapy

Physical therapy

Speech therapy

Where does he/she go for these therapy services? *

Your answer _____

Send me a copy of my responses.

[Back](#)

[Submit](#)

Page 2 of 2

[Clear form](#)

Appendix E

Filipino translation of focus group discussion questions

Filipino translation of the focus group discussion questions for participants regarding the Z benefit package for CDDs

1. Paano mo nalaman ang Z benefit package para sa mga batang may developmental disabilities?
2. Sa kasalukuyang pangkalusugang sistema at estado ng mga batang may developmental disabilities, ano sa tingin mo ang “impact” o epekto ng Z benefit package?
3. Ano ang masasabi mo sa nilalaman ng Z benefit package?
4. Ano ang masasabi mo sa mga prosesong kailangan isagawa para sa implementasyon ng Z benefit package?
5. Bilang isang _____, ano ang iyong papel at tungkulin sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package para sa mga batang may developmental disabilities?
6. Ano ang antas ng iyong interes sa pakikilahok sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?
7. Sa paanong paraan ka maaaring makatulong sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?
8. Ano sa tingin mo ang mga balakid sa epektibong pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?
9. Ano sa tingin mo ang mga bagay na tumutulong sa epektibong pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?
10. Ano ang iyong mga rekomendasyon/suhestisyon para mapalawak ang pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?

Filipino translation of specific questions for FGD cohorts

Cohorts	With experience in implementation of the Z benefit package for CDDs	Without experience in implementation of the Z benefit package for CDDs
<p>Managerial and administration heads of HCI offering rehabilitation services for CDDs</p>	<p>Anu-anong preparasyon ang isinagawa ng iyong institusyon para makilahok sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package para sa mga batang may kapansanan?</p> <p>Anu-ano ang mga naging adjustments na nangyari sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?</p> <p>Papaano nahahanay ang Z benefit package sa misyon/layunin ng iyong institusyon?</p>	<p>Ano ang iyong pananaw sa mga requirements at sa potensyal na pagiging accredited ng iyong institusyon?</p> <p>Nakikita mo ba ang posibilidad na ma-accredit ang iyong institusyon sa nalalapit na panahon? Bakit oo o bakit hindi?</p> <p>Anu-anong klaseng adjustments ang maaaring maisagawa para makalahok sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?</p> <p>Papaano nahahanay ang Z benefit package sa misyon/layunin ng iyong institusyon?</p>

<p>Health Professionals</p>	<p>Paano nakaapekto ang implementasyon ng Z benefit package sa iyong trabaho bilang isang health professional?</p> <p>Anong aspeto ng iyong trabaho ang naimpluwensyahan ng Z benefit package?</p> <p>Base sa iyong clinical expertise, ano ang masasabi mo sa mga kinakailangang kagamitan na nakasaad sa eligibility criteria para ma-accredit ang inyong institusyon?</p>	<p>Paano makakaapekto ang implementasyon ng Z benefit package sa iyong trabaho bilang isang health professional?</p> <p>Base sa iyong clinical expertise, ano ang masasabi mo sa mga kinakailangang kagamitan na nakasaad sa eligibility criteria para ma-accredit ang isang institusyon?</p>
<p>Civil Society Organizations Representatives</p>	<p>Paano ka nakalahok sa pagsasagawa o pagformulate sa Z benefit package?</p> <p>Sa kasalukuyan, paano ka nakikilahok sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?</p> <p>Paano nahahanay ang Z benefit package sa misyon/layunin ng iyong organisasyon?</p>	<p>Sa kasalukuyan, paano kayo maaaring makilahok sa pagpapatupad ng Z benefit package?</p> <p>Paano nahahanay ang Z benefit package sa misyon/layunin ng iyong organisasyon?</p>

<p>Parents of CDDs</p>	<p>Kumusta ang iyong karanasan sa paggamit ng Z benefit package?</p> <p>Paano nakaapekto ang Z benefit package sa iyong anak na may developmental disability?</p> <p>Sa iyong palagay, ano ang mga kailangang maisagawa para mas maraming batang may kapansanan at pamilya ang makatanggap ng benepisyo sa PhilHealth?</p>	<p>Ano ang posibilidad na makapagbenepisyo ka sa Z benefit package?</p> <p>Kung hindi ka nakakatanggap ng benepisyo sa Z benefit package, paano mo itinataguyod ang kailangan funds para ma-assess at makapagtherapy ang iyong anak na may developmental disability?</p>
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Appendix F

Summary of codes from the FGD

Policy Elements	Facilitators	Barriers
Context	<p>Campaign for early intervention and continuous sessions impact child's development which may potentially reach ~2 million CDDs</p> <p>Increased accessibility may provide a sense of relief and help them have better family dynamics</p> <p>Alignment with existing laws</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● revised Guiding Principles of Z benefit package to follow provisions of RA 11032: Ease of Doing Business Act and RA 11223 Universal Healthcare Act ● emphasis on No Balance Billing Policy to follow provisions of RA 10606 National Health Insurance Act <p>Passing of relevant laws</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● passing of SLP law may increase opportunities for promotion and opening of more plantilla positions in hospitals ● trust in PhilHealth as policy is supported by universal healthcare law <p>Presence of legislative representation in Congress</p>	<p>Package has low impact as of present due to limited access to therapy services in most provinces</p> <p>Financial burden can be felt by families regardless of socio-economic status</p> <p>Issues in politics and governance in the country</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● poor laws and policies implementation in the country ● absence of 'developmental disabilities' category in PWD ID based on Magna Carta for PWD ● lack of trust in PhilHealth by the private sector due to corruption-related issues ● redundancy of having a package in public hospitals which offer free or subsidized therapy services already <p>Issues related to employment of professionals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● limited plantilla items in public hospitals for rehabilitation professionals ● low supply of rehabilitation professionals compared to the demand ● brain drain of rehabilitation professionals <p>Implementation of the package was disrupted due to COVID-19 pandemic</p>

Actors	<p>Involvement during policy formulation and implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● disabled people organizations for CDDs and professional organizations were involved during policy formulation ● professionals working in accredited institution were involved during the contracting process <p>Administrative advantage of public sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● higher management's strong support in accredited HCI ● presence of PhilHealth coordinator in the public HCI ● being accustomed and more accepting of the various processes involved in the implementation <p>Alignment with values and advocacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● willingness to participate in the implementation of the package ● equitability in service provision is part of values of public and private institutions; and professional organizations ● openness to collaborate with other groups/organizations as one body to further push advocacies ● stakeholders' proactive role to negotiate during policy reform and to reevaluate equitability of access 	<p>Lack of involvement of potential service providers (both public and private HCI) and pediatric rehabilitation experts during policy formulation</p> <p>Human resource issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● absence of PhilHealth coordinator in private HCI ● small number of full-time professionals compared to part-time professionals ● preference of most professionals to be employed in private HCI instead of public HCI ● leadership turnover in agencies and organizations <p>Help received in disability sector is focused on receiving allowance instead of services</p>
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Content	<p>Generally comprehensive and complete list of services and rates</p> <p>Presence of a separate document containing list of frequently asked questions in the Filipino language (Tagalog)</p> <p>Organized and easy to follow through proper sectioning and use of visual information</p>	<p>Inadequate costing of services</p> <p>Concerns on required resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● lack of specificity in materials required ● inclusion of unnecessary resources ● limited scope of assessment tools required in terms developmental domains, indications and cultural validity <p>Absence of certain protocols</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● lack of protocol for specialized treatment sessions ● lack of protocol for accreditation of rehabilitation professionals ● lack of COVID-19 protocols for facilities
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<p>Process</p>	<p>Numerous information dissemination reports released in various media during launch</p> <p>Subcontracting private professionals via the contracted HCI</p> <p>Assuring quality of implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● importance of having accreditation and contracting standards ● importance of documentation ● inclusion of clauses for policy review for evaluation and monitoring <p>Extension of validity of approved pre-authorization applications with the package as consideration due to COVID-19 pandemic</p>	<p>Issues in information dissemination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● failure to mention the lack of contracted HCI during initial launch ● lack of information dissemination efforts to potential service providers <p>Lack of stakeholder engagement activities from PhilHealth</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● lack of visits in capable service providers in the private sector ● lack of follow-up from PhilHealth staff ● lack of official orientation on contracting process and implementation proper ● lack of timely update on policy review and needed reform <p>Tediousness of the processes for accreditation, contracting, and filing of claims for reimbursement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● preparing budget for procurement, shipping equipment and tools from abroad, and additional training of staff ● filling out numerous forms across all steps ● anticipated delays in reimbursement of claims for service providers <p>Limited number of sessions to merit re-evaluation before client enrolls to another set of therapy sessions</p>
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Appendix G

Informed Consent Forms

INFORMED CONSENT [ENGLISH VERSION]

Informed Consent Form for Participants in the study entitled “Disability Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities in the Philippines: A Policy Analysis”

Pauline Gail V. Martinez

University of the Philippines Open University

Master of International Health Thesis

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction

I am Pauline Gail V. Martinez, **a graduate student in UPOU and the investigator of this study in partial fulfillment of my Master of International Health degree.** As a

_____ (manager/rehabilitation professional/board member in professional organization/parent of a child with developmental disabilities), you are invited as a participant in the focus group discussion about the PhilHealth Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities (CDDs). If you have any questions/clarifications about this study, please feel free to contact me and I will be happy to answer your queries.

Purpose

This study seeks to analyze the factors that influence the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs in the Philippines.

The following specific research objectives are formulated:

- 1) Describe the current context, actors, content and process of the disability benefit package for CDDs
- 2) Explore perspectives of actors towards implementation of the disability benefit package and their critiques on the context, content and process of the policy
- 3) Determine the facilitators and barriers that influence the implementation of the disability benefit package for CDDs

Type of Research Intervention

To participate in this study, you will be undergoing a focus group discussion which is estimated to approximately 90 to 120 minutes. The focus group discussion will be conducted via an online video conferencing platform (i.e. Zoom Video Communications).

Participant Selection

You are selected to participate in this research because of your substantial role in your organization, profession, society or a parent of a child with developmental disability. Your perspective about this policy (Z benefit package for CDDs) will be helpful in order to identify factors that influence its current state of implementation. A total of 16 participants is expected to participate in the study which will be divided into 4 groups with 4 participants each. Once confirmed, you will be joined by other three participants in the group of the same background (i.e. managers/administrators, rehabilitation professionals, board members of professional organizations, parents of CDDs).

Voluntary Participation

As a participant, you have the right to refuse or withdraw your participation. When the focus group discussion has already begun/completed, you may request that the information you have provided not be used in the study.

Procedures

Once you have accepted participation, an email will be sent to you regarding the meeting details and schedule.

A focus group discussion will be conducted with other participants of similar background and the principal investigator via an online video conference platform. Permission to record the meeting via the video conference platform or an audio recorder will be asked. General set of questions will be sent to you after your confirmation of participation. Probing questions may be asked.

All information will be kept confidential and focus group discussion transcripts will be saved in a password-protected file and laptop. Pseudonyms will be used to maintain

privacy and confidentiality. All data used in the study will be discarded one year after the study has been completed.

Duration

Aside from the 90 to 120-minute discussion, participants will be reached during the data analysis process to validate the analysis of the results. Participants will be given at least two weeks to respond and a follow-up will be given after the first week. If there are no responses given, this will be considered that the participant agrees with the initial interpretation and analysis.

Risks

There are no directed risks associated with the study. However, if the participant becomes uncomfortable, he/she may not answer a specific question or may opt to discontinue participation.

Benefits

Information about the PhilHealth Z benefit package for CDDs will be given and may spark interest of participants/institutions to participate as an accredited healthcare provider. Once the study is completed, recommendations may be used as evidence for policy reform that may lead to improvement of implementation and improvement of access to healthcare services.

Reimbursements

Participating to this study is voluntary, thus no corresponding compensation will be given. However, participants are entitled to receive reimbursement for expenses (i.e. internet data) incurred as a result of their participation. Token of appreciation such as food vouchers will also be provided amounting to P200.00.

Confidentiality

All information provided will be treated as confidential. Pseudonyms will be assigned to participants. Only role and type of sector (for professionals involved) shall be associated with the direct quotations in the process of reporting results of the study.

Sharing the results

Once the study has been completed, the participants will be informed and key findings will be shared via email. A copy of the full manuscript may also be given as requested.

Right to refuse or withdraw

It is emphasized that participants have the right to refuse and withdraw from the study at any time.

Data Management

Focus group discussion transcripts will be saved in a Word document in a password protected file and laptop. The raw data will be available to the principal investigator and the research adviser only. All data from the study will be discarded, one year after the study has been completed.

Who to contact

For further information and questions, you may contact:

Dr. Michael P. Sy

Adviser | Principal Investigator

mpsy@up.edu.ph / +6395600256627

The study has been approved by the UPM Research Ethics Board (UPM REB) and may be reached through the following contact for information regarding the rights of study participants, including grievances and complaints.

Dr. Cecilia Jimeno

Address: Room 126, Ground Floor

National Institutes of Health, UP Manila

623 Pedro Gil St.

Ermita 1000 Manila

Email: upmreb@post.upm.edu.ph

Tel: +63 2 8526-434

Part II: Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]: _____

INFORMED CONSENT [FILIPINO VERSION]

Informed Consent Form para sa mga Makikilahok sa Pananaliksik na pinamagatang “Disability Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities in the Philippines: A Policy Analysis”

Pauline Gail V. Martinez

University of the Philippines Open University

Master of International Health Thesis

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction

Ako si Pauline Gail V. Martinez, **isang graduate student sa UPOU at nanaliksik bilang parte ng aking pag-aaral bilang sa aking degree – Master of International Health.** Bilang isang _____ (manager/rehabilitation professional/officer sa professional organization/magulang ng isang anak ng batang may kapansanan), iniimbita kitang makilahok sa isang focus group discussion o talakayan ukol sa PhilHealth Z Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities (CDDs). Kung mayroon kang mga katanungan o paglilinaw, huwag mag-atubiling kausapin ako upang bigyan ka pa ng iyong mga kinakailangang impormasyon.

Purpose

Ang layunin ng pananaliksik na ito ay para i-analyze ang mga bagay na nakaka-impluwensya sa implementasyon ng disability benefit package for CDDs sa Pilipinas. Ang mga particular na layunin na kabilang dito ay:

- 1.) Ilarawan ang konteksto, aktor, nilalaman at proseso ng disability benefit package for CDDs
- 2.) Alamin ang mga pananaw ng mga aktor (taong sangkot sa polisiya) ukol sa pagpapatupad ng disability benefit package at ang kanilang mga kritiko sa konteksto, nilalaman at proseso ng polisiya
- 3.) Tukuyin ang mga suporta at balakid na nakaka-impluwensya sa implementasyon ng disability benefit package for CDDs

Type of Research Intervention

Upang makalahok, ikaw ay makakasama sa isang focus group discussion o talakayan na magtatagal nang 90 to 120 minuto. Ang talakayan ay isasagawa sa online video conferencing platform (i.e. Zoom Video Communications).

Participant Selection

Ikaw ay napiling makilahok sa pag-aaral na ito dahil sa iyong mahalagang tungkulin sa iyong organisasyon, propesyon, o bilang isang magulang ng isang batang may developmental disability. Ang iyong pananaw ukol sa polisiya na ito (Z benefit package for CDDs) ay makakatulong upang lubos na mapag-aralan at matukoy ang mga bagay na nakakaapekto sa kasalukuyang implementasyon nito. Labing-anim (16) na tao ang inaasahang makasali. Magkakaroon ng apat na grupo na may tig-apat na kalahok. Kapag ikaw ay nagkumpirma ng partisipasyon, makakasama mo ang tatlong iba pang kalahok na may katulad mong tungkulin. (i.e. managers/administrators/ rehabilitation professionals/ boards members ng professional organizations, magulang ng CDDs).

Voluntary Participation

Bilang isang kalahok, ikaw ay may karapatang tumanggi o bawiin ang iyong pagsang-ayon sa pakikilahok dito. Kung naganap na ang talakayan, maaari mo ring bawiin ang impormasyon na iyong naibahagi.

Procedures

Kapag iyong kunipirma na ang pakikilahok sa focus group discussion, makatatanggap ka ng mensahe ukol sa detalye at schedule ng talakayan.

Ang focus group discussion o talakayan ay gaganapin sa isang online video conferencing. Makakasama mo ang tatlo pang kalahok na may parehas na tungkulin bilang isang manager/rehabilitation professional/ board member ng professional organization/ magulang ng isang batang may kapansanan. Hihingi ako ng pahintulot para i-record the meeting gamit ang video conference platform at isang audio recorder. Ang listahan ng general na katanungan ay maibibigay rin bago ang nakatakdang talakayan. Maaaring magtanong pa ng ibang katanungan bilang magbigay ng linaw o maghingi ng mas particular na impormasyon/pananaw.

Lahat ng maibabahaging impormasyon ay mananatiling confidential. Gagamit ng pseudonyms o ibang pangalan sa pagsasagawa ng transcripts. Ang mga transcripts ay ilalagay sa isang password-protected file at laptop. Ang mga ito ay buburahin matapos maisagawa ang kabuuang pananaliksik.

Duration

Maliban sa 90 to 120-minutong focus group discussion, aanyayahan din ang mga kalahok na i-validate o i-check ang analysis ng mga nakuhang impormasyon. Ang mga kalahok ay bibigyan ng dalawang linggo upang tumugon. Isang follow-up message ang matatanggap matapos ang isang linggo. Kung ang kalahok ay hindi sumagot, ito ay ikokonsider na pagsang-ayon sa analysis ng pag-aaral.

Risks

Walang partikular na risks o panganib ang maaaring maranasa sa pakikilahok. Subalit, kung may pagkakataon na nagging hindi komportable sa katanungan ang nakikilahok, maaaring tumanggi sa pagsagot ng katanungan o itigil ang pakikilahok sa focus group discussion.

Benefits

Ang maibibigay na impormasyon ukol sa PhilHealth Z benefit package for CDDs ay maaaring makatulong sa mga nakilahok upang magamit ang benefit package o pag-isipan ang pakikilahok sa PhilHealth bilang isang accredited healthcare provider. Kapag naisagawa na ang kabuuang pananaliksik, ang mga pananaw at rekomendasyong naitala ay maaaring maging bahagi ng policy reforms.

Reimbursements

Dahil ang partisipasyon dito ay kusang-loob, walang katumbas na kabayaran ang pagsali. Subalit, Ang mga kalahok ay maaaring makatanggap ng reimbursement sa expenses (i.e. internet data) upang makilahok sa focus group discussion.

Makatatanggap rin ang mga kalahok ng simpleng token of appreciation tulad ng food vouchers na nagkakahalagang P200.00.

Confidentiality

Lahat ng personal na impormasyon na maibibigay ay mananatili lamang sa pagitan ng mga kalahok sa focus group discussion at ng principal investigator. Sa pagsusulat ng transcripts, magkakaroon ng pseudonym ang lahat ng kalahok. Ang role at kabilang na sektor na kinabibilangan lamang ang mababanggit sa pagrereport ng resulta ng pananaliksik.

Sharing the results

Kapag natapos na ang pananaliksik, ibabahagi sa mga kalahok ang buod ng pananaliksik. Maaaring makakuha ng buong kopya ng manuscript kung ito man ay hilingin.

Right to refuse or withdraw

Ang partisipasyon sa focus group discussion ay *voluntary*. Ikaw ay may karapatan tumanggi o bawiin ang pagsang-ayon sa pakikilahok sa talakayan.

Data Management

Ang focus group discussion transcripts ay ilalagay sa isang Word document sa password protected file and laptop. Tanging ang principal investigator at ang research adviser lamang ang makakakita sa transcripts. Lahat ng data ay buburahin, isang taon matapos maisagawa ang pananaliksik.

Who to contact

Para sa karagdagang impormasyon at katanungan, maaaring makipag-ugnayan kay:

Dr. Michael P. Sy

Adviser | Principal Investigator

mpsy@up.edu.ph / +6395600256627

Ang pananaliksik na ito ay na-aprubahan ng UP Manila Research Ethics Board (UPM REB). Maaaring silang kausapin o tawagan ukol sa mga impormasyon katulad ng karapatan ng mga kalahok – kabilang na rin ang mga hinaing o anumang reklamo.

Dr. Cecilia Jimeno

Address: Room 126, Ground Floor

National Institutes of Health, UP Manila

623 Pedro Gil St.

Ermita 1000 Manila

Email: upmreb@post.upm.edu.ph

Tel: +63 2 8526-4346

Part II: Certificate of Consent

Nabasa ako ang mga impormasyong nakasaad o nabanggit sa akin ang lahat ng impormasyon. Nagkaroon ako ng pagkakatong magtanong at natugunan nang sapat at maayos ang aking mga katanungan. Pumapayag akong makilahok sa focus group discussion ng pananaliksik na ito.

Pangalan: _____

Pirma: _____

Petsa: [MM/DD/YYYY]: _____

APPENDIX H

Certificate of exemption from UP Manila Research Ethics Board

UPMREB FORM4(Q)2019: REQUEST FOR UPMREB CERTIFICATION OF EXEMPTION FROM ETHICAL REVIEW
03/11/2021

University of the Philippines Manila
RESEARCH ETHICS BOARD
Room 126, National Institutes of Health, UP Manila
623 Pedro Gil Street, Ermita, 1000 Manila
Telephone: +63 2 8526-4346; Email: upmreb@post.upm.edu.ph

REQUEST FOR UPMREB CERTIFICATION OF EXEMPTION FROM ETHICAL REVIEW

The University of the Philippines Manila Research Ethics Board UPMREB Review Panel 1 has processed your request for *EXEMPTION FROM ETHICAL REVIEW* for the following study protocol and related documents which has been reviewed with resulting panel conditions and considerations:

UPMREB CODE: UPMREB 2022-0361-EX
SUBMISSION DATE: 04 July 2022
STUDY PROTOCOL TITLE: Disability Benefit Package for Children with Developmental Disabilities in the Philippines: A Policy Analysis
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. Michael Palapal Sy
SPONSOR/FUNDING AGENCY: Investigator
DATE OF ACTION: 08 July 2022
JUSTIFICATION FOR THIS CERTIFICATION: <ul style="list-style-type: none">The study protocol qualified with the criteria for exemption as stipulated under provision 3.1 page 38 in the National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-related Research 2017, While there are human participants, the FGD questions are unlikely to cause any risks of mental or psychological distress. These methodologies outlined in this protocol involves negligible risks.
Document/s included in the review on which this certification was based: <ol style="list-style-type: none">Study Protocol version 1; submitted 04 July 2022;Informed Consent (English Version) submitted 04 July 2022;Informed Consent (Tagalog Version) submitted 04 July 2022;
Composition of Team on Record: <ol style="list-style-type: none">Composition of Research Team on Record:<ul style="list-style-type: none">Dr. Michael Palapal Sy as principal investigator andMs. Pauline Gail Martinez as co – investigator.

Page 1 of 2

UPMREB 2022-0361-EX_Exemption_Sy

RESPONSIBILITIES OF PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR WHILE STUDY IS IN PROGRESS:

1. Continuing compliance with the exemption criteria of the National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-Related Research 2017 in the duration of the study;
2. No substantial changes in research design, methodology and subject population from the protocol submitted for exemption. Modifications that significantly affect previous risk-benefit assessment or qualification for exemption may be submitted as new protocol for initial review.
3. Notice of termination of the study using 3(C)2012: Final Report Form

All further queries regarding this request may be forwarded to the undersigned through upmreb@post.upm.edu.ph or telephone number +63 2 8526-4346.

CECILIA A. JIMENO, MD
Chair, UPMREB Review Panel 1

Appendix I

Curriculum Vitae

PAULINE GAIL V. MARTINEZ, OTRP

Occupational Therapy Educator and Practitioner | paulinegailmartinez@gmail.com | +639267081860

Education

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES OPEN UNIVERSITY – Faculty of Management and Development Studies

Aug 2021 – present, Master of International Health

Dec 2021, Diploma in International Health

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES MANILA – College of Allied Medical Professions

Jun 2016 | Bachelor of Science in Occupational Therapy (OT)

Awards: Merit Awardee, Outstanding Student Clinician, Best in Research Presentation

PAMPANGA HIGH SCHOOL

Mar 2012 | High School Diploma

Award: Fifth Honorable Mention, Best in Public Speaking, Best in Journalism

SAN FERNANDO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Mar 2008 | Elementary Diploma

Award: Batch Salutatorian

Experience

July 2021 - Present	<i>Program Chair, Department of Occupational Therapy, College of Allied Medical Professions, Angeles University Foundation</i>
May 2019 – June 2021	<i>Internship Coordinator, Department of Occupational Therapy, College of Allied Medical Professions, Angeles University Foundation</i>
Jul 2017 - Present	<i>Part-time Faculty Member, Department of Occupational Therapy, College of Allied Medical Professions, Angeles University Foundation</i>
Jul 2017 - Present	<i>Occupational Therapy Consultant, Play Matters Therapy Center (Pampanga)</i>
Aug 2016 - Jul 2017	<i>College Instructor, Department of Occupational Therapy, College of Allied Medical Professions, University of the Philippines Manila</i>
Mar - Apr 2016	<i>Intern, Innovations and Change Management in Collaboration Course, Department of Community Medicine and Rehabilitation, Umeå University</i>
Jan - Mar 2016	<i>Intern, Hand and Plastics Surgery Clinic, Umeå University Hospital, Sweden</i>
Dec 2015	<i>Intern, Department of Rehabilitation Medicine – Occupational Therapy (Adult Section), Philippine General Hospital</i>
Oct – Nov 2015	<i>Intern, Clinic for Therapy Services – Pediatrics, UP-CAMP</i>
Aug - Sep 2015	<i>Intern, Community-Based Rehabilitation Services, Bustos, Bulacan</i> <i>Facilitator and Proponent, Projects: "Kaibigan, May "K" Ka" (PWD rights advocacy) and "Taralets Bagets" (Youth Project with Involvement of Adolescents with Intellectual Disabilities)</i>

Research

- Oct 2021 Martinez, P.G.V, Pineda, R.C., Sy, M.P, De Vera, C.K. M., Galang, M.M.R.F., Cayanan, K.K.S., & Musni, M.P.A.P. (2021). Experiences and reflections of clinical supervisors on online occupational therapy internship during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Philippine Journal of Health Research and Development*. <https://pihrd.upm.edu.ph/index.php/main/article/view/520>
- Jan 2021 Sy, M.P., Martinez, P.G., & Twinley, R. (2021). The dark side of occupation within the context of modern-day beauty pageants. *Work*, xx. doi.10.3233/WOR-205055
- Jan 2019 Sy, M. P., Martinez, P. G., Labung, F. F., Medina, M. A., Mesina, A. S., Vicencio, M. R., & Tulabut, H. D. (2019). Baseline assessment on the quality of interprofessional collaboration among Filipino Mental Health Professionals. *Journal of Interprofessional Education & Practice*, 14, 58-66. doi:10.1016/j.xjep.2018.12.003
- Sept 2018 Sy, M. P., Martinez, P. G., Labung, F. F., Medina, M. A., Mesina, A. S., Vicencio M. R., & Tulabut, H. D. (2018). Are we a quality mental health care team: Baseline assessment on the quality of interprofessional collaboration among Filipino mental health professionals. [Poster Presentation], *All Together Better Health IX (New Zealand)*. doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35351.01440
- Sept 2017 Blas, A.J.T., Beltran, K.M.B., Martinez, P.G.V., & Yao, D.P.G. (2017). Enabling work: Occupational therapy interventions for persons with occupational injuries and diseases – a scoping review. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*. doi: 10.1007/s10926-017-9732-

Management and Administration

- August 2021 Proponent and Clinical Director, Kayantabe Occupational Therapy Mental Health Clinic, Angeles University Foundation
- Proponent and Academic Supervisor, (Revised) Academic and Administrative Training in OT education, Department of Occupational Therapy, College of Allied Medical Professions, Angeles University Foundation
- Jan 2021 Proponent and Preceptor, AUF Occupational Therapy Community-Based Rehabilitation Training Program
- Aug 2017-present Course Lead/Coordinator in various courses:
OT1: Foundations in Occupational Therapy 1
OT2: Foundations in Occupational Therapy 2
TSOT: Therapeutic Skills in Occupational Therapy
LMOT: Leadership and Management in Occupational Therapy
OT4b: Occupational Therapy Evaluation in Physical Dysfunction
Res1: Foundations of Occupational Therapy Research
Res2: Research Proposal Writing
Res3: Research Writing and Implementation

Aug 2019	Organizing member and volunteer, Therafree, Free therapy screening and home programs, Minalin, Pampanga
Nov 2018	Organizing member and volunteer, Therafree, Free therapy screening and home programs, City of San Fernando, Pampanga
Aug 2016 - 2017	Course Lead/Coordinator, OT122: Occupational Therapy Theory Course Lead/Coordinator, OT103: Kinesiology in Occupational Therapy Member, UP CAMP Research Committee Member, UP CAMP Gender Committee Member, UP CAMP Extension Committee Member, UP Manila Gender Committee
Apr 2016	<i>Project head</i> , "Promoting Client-Centeredness in Hemmavis Baseline Assessment Questionnaire" in collaboration with the Department of Computing Sciences and Department of Community Medicine and Rehabilitation, Umeå University
Mar 2016	<i>Proponent</i> , "OT Interventions for Persons with Hand Osteoarthritis" Development Plan in Hand and Plastics Surgery Clinic, Umeå University

Awards, Scholarships, Honors Received

Feb 2021	International Publication Award, Angeles University Foundation
July 2019	International Publication Award, Angeles University Foundation
Feb 2017	License No. 00003476, Occupational Therapist Registered, Philippines, Philippine Regulatory Commission
Jun 2016	Merit Awardee Best Research Presentation Outstanding Student Clinician Best Intern in Community-based Rehabilitation College Recognition, UP-CAMP
Oct 2015	Awardee, Linnaeus-Palme Exchange Student Program (International Scholarship, Sweden)

Special Lectures, Seminars and Conferences Attended

Nov 2021	Delegate, Asia Pacific Occupational Therapy Congress
Sep 2021	Guest Lecturer, Department of Occupational Therapy, Tokyo Metropolitan University Participant, REHAB Insights Quo Vadis
Aug 2021	Delegate, Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc. General Assembly
July 2021	Speaker, All About Occupations Session 3: The doings and occupations of

	those who desire to be "beautiful". University of Brighton. United Kingdom. Microsoft Teams.
	Speaker, Kalusugan at Kaunlaran ng Pilipinong May Kapansanan, Isulong sa Gitna ng Pandemya, National Disability Prevention and Rehabilitation Week, Jose B. Lingad Memorial Hospital
Jun 2021	Organizer, Interprofessional Education Training of Trainers, Angeles University Foundation
May 2021	Cultivating Collaboration, Fostering Interprofessionalism in Healthcare. University of Santo Tomas, Zoom Video Communications. All About Occupations. Session 1. The COVID-19 pandemic and ensuing occupational disruption: Exposing the lie that "we're all in this together" by Karen Whalley Hammel. University of Brighton, UK. Microsoft Teams.
Mar 2021	Organizer, Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc. Central Luzon Chapter First General Assembly, Zoom Video Communications.
Dec 2020	Organizer and Commission on Elections Head, Cabalen Occupational Therapists' First General Assembly, Zoom Video Communications.
Oct 2020	Essentials on Global Health, Yale University, Coursera Online Course Chapter 3: Re-imagining OT Education in a Changing World, Occupassion, Zoom Video Communications. Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc. Educator's Forum, Zoom Video Communications.
June 2020	Occupational Therapy Clinical Education Forum, Department of Occupational Therapy, College of Allied Medical Professions, Angeles University Foundation Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) Practitioner Certificate, Achology & Udemy (Online Course). Certificate of completion. Learning to teach online. The University of New South Wales. Coursera.
May 2020	COVID-19 World Health Organization Online Courses: Infection Prevention and Control for Novel Coronavirus COVID-19: How to put on and remove personal protective equipment Standard Precautions: Hand hygiene Standard Precautions: Waste management
Mar 2020	Warp Speed Download: Essential Info to Jumpstart your Teletherapy Practice How to Know What works: Evidence for Telepractice and Beyond Creating and Adapting Therapy Materials for Telepractice Teletherapy: Tips to Keep Young Children Engaged from ASHA. Bright Ideas (Online Course)

Oct 2018	TheraCon 2018: Fostering Globally Competent Healthcare and Education Professionals Towards Building Strong and Sustainable Communities, Unilab Bayanihan Center, Pasig City
	CHED Outcomes-based Education Training: Luzon Run, Royce Hotel Clark, Pampanga
Aug 2018	Speaker, "Collaboration as a 21 st Century Skill: Introduction to TEAM Protocol", 1 st Philippine Interprofessional Education and Collaboration, University of Sto. Tomas, Manila
Jan 2018	Getting Handwriting Right Workshop, UP-NCPAG, Quezon City
Nov 2017	52 nd Annual Convention of the Philippines Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc., Century Park Hotel Manila, Pasay City, Metro Manila
	Disaster Risk Reduction Workshop, Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc., Play Matters Therapy Center, Mexico, Pampanga
Sep 2017	9 th Biennial Philippine Society for Behavioral and Developmental Pediatrics, Novotel, Quezon City
Aug 2017	Early Childhood Milestones Congress by The Clark Medical City, Holy Angel University, Pampanga
Oct 2016	Workshop on Outcomes-based Education: Faculty Orientation (4 Sessions). UP National Teacher Training Center for Health Professions. UP Manila.
July 2016	Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc., Midyear Assembly,, University of Perpetual Help – Las Pinas, Manila
Nov 2015	Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists 50 th Founding Anniversary Celebration, Makati City
	Promoting Social Participation for Older Persons through Supported Information Technology Lecture, Prof. Caroline Fischl (Visiting Professor from Umea University), UP-CAMP
	Goal Attainment Scaling Lecture, Prof. Caroline Fischl (Visiting Professor from Umea University), UP-CAMP
	Occupational Therapy Intervention Process Model (Visiting Professor from Umea University), Prof. Caroline Fischl, UP-CAMP
	Back to Basics in Splinting, Department of Rehabilitation Medicine, Philippine General Hospital, Ermita, Manila
Sep 2015	Occupation-based hand therapy and hand rehabilitation as a career path, Kathlyn Huntern OTR/L, CHT, UP-CAMP
Jul 2015	Handling the child with cerebral palsy: Seminar workshop for students, Hong's Center for Children with Cerebral Palsy, Ortigas Metro Manila

May 2015 Established and Emerging Practices: The Evolution of Occupational Therapy in the Philippines, Occupational Therapy Students Assembly 2015, Quezon City Manila.

Affiliations and Memberships

Mar 2021 - present	Founding Member, Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists Inc. Central Luzon Chapter
April 2019 – Dec 2020	Public Relations Officer, Cabalen Occupational Therapists
Nov 2015 - Present	Regular Member, Philippine Academy of Occupational Therapists, Inc.

Interests

Volunteer work (Youth Service, Community Work, PWD Advocacy)
Hosting and Organizing Programs and Events
Music (Choir singing, playing musical instruments)
Travelling

Character References

Michael P. Sy, PhD, MHPed, OTRP
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